

**DEVELOPMENT OF A REMOTE HYPERTENSION MONITORING AND RISK
STRATIFICATION MODEL USING PERCENTILE RANK BASED MULTI-
CRITERIA DECISION MAKING ALGORITHM**

BY

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**A THESIS SUBMITTED TO THE POSTGRADUATE SCHOOL, FEDERAL
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FULFILLMENT OF THE REQUIREMENTS FOR THE AWARD OF THE DEGREE
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FEBRUARY, 2025

DECLARATION

I hereby declare that this thesis titled “Development of a Remote Hypertension Monitoring and Risk Stratification Model Using Percentile Rank Based Multi-criteria Decision Making Algorithm” is a collection of my original research work and it has not been presented for any other qualification anywhere. Information from other sources (published or unpublished) has been duly acknowledged.

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CERTIFICATION

This thesis titled “Development of a Remote Hypertension Monitoring and Risk Stratification Model Using Percentile Rank Based Multi-criteria Decision Making Algorithm” by ATABO Onuche Gideon (PhD/SICT/2019/9834) meets the regulations governing the award of the degree of PhD of the Federal University of Technology, Minna and it is approved for its contribution to scientific knowledge and literary presentation..

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DEDICATION

This research work is dedicated to my wife (Martha Atabo), my children (Samson Yagbo Atabo, Sarah Yache Atabo, Salvation Yajadu Atabo and Sophia Yafedo Atabo), my Father Samson Yenusa Atabo.

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ABSTRACT

Hypertension, a leading risk factor for cardiovascular diseases (CVDs), poses a significant health challenge, particularly in low- and middle-income countries (LMICs), where healthcare access and resources are limited. Existing remote hypertension monitoring and risk stratification systems often face issues related to complexity, lack of interpretability, and failure to account for the multifactorial nature of hypertension, limiting their practical application. This study addresses these challenges by developing a remote hypertension monitoring and risk stratification model using the Percentile Rank-Based Multi-criteria Decision Making algorithm (PRBMCDM). The study aims to identify and prioritise hypertension risk factors, design hypertension risk stratification model using PRBMCDM algorithm, implement/stimulate the designed model and evaluate the model's performance using standard metrics, including accuracy, precision, recall, F-score, and Area under the Curve (AUC). Data were collected from public and private hospitals in Kogi Eastern Senatorial District, Nigeria, and analysed using descriptive statistics and feature importance techniques such as drop column importance. The PRBMCDM framework integrates multiple health parameters, including age, gender, family history, hypertension grade, and total cholesterol, to stratify patients into high, medium, and low-risk groups. The model achieved high classification accuracy and demonstrated strong performance across risk categories, with AUC values of 0.987, 0.987, and 0.968 for high, medium, and low-risk groups, respectively. The findings highlight the model's ability to balance predictive accuracy with clinical interpretability, making it suitable for resource-constrained settings. Recommendations include the integration of PRBMCDM into healthcare systems, pilot testing in clinical settings, and the incorporation of real-time data from Internet of Things (IoT) devices to enhance its responsiveness. The study contributes to knowledge by offering a comprehensive, interpretable, and effective solution for hypertension risk management, with potential applications in other chronic diseases.

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LIST OF ACRONYMS

Acronyms	Meaning as Used in This Study
ACA	American College of Cardiology
AHP	Analytic Hierarchy Process
AHA	American Heart Association
ANFIS	Adaptive Neuro-Fuzzy Inference System
BLE	Bluetooth Low Energy
BNP	Brain Natriuretic Peptide
CDVS	Cardiovascular Disease
CGM	Continuous Glucose Monitoring
CHD	Coronary Heart Disease
CRP	C-reactive Protein
DBP	Diastolic Blood Pressure
GFR	Glomerular Filtration Rate
HBP	High Blood Pressure
HMOD	Hypertension Mediated Organ Damage
IoT	Internet of Things
ISH	International Society of Hypertension
LMICs	Low-and-Middle-Income Countries
LV	Left Ventricular

MAUT	Multi-Attribute Utility Theory
MESA	Multi-Ethnic Study of Atherosclerosis
MCDM	Multi-Criteria Decision-Making
NodeMCU	Node MicroController
PRBMCDM	Percentile Rank based Multi-criteria Decision Making
RFID	Radio Frequency Identification
RHMS	Remote Health Monitoring System
SBP	Systolic Blood Pressure
SMART	Second Manifestations of ARterial disease
SNPs	Single Nucleotide Polymorphisms
TCDMA	Time Criticality Based Decision Making Algorithm
TOLF	The Optimal Lymph Flow
TOPSIS	Technique for Order of Preference by Similarity to Ideal Solution
WHA	World Health Assembly
WHO	World Health Organization

CHAPTER ONE

1.0

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background to the Study

The prevalence of non-communicable disease (NCD) globally is worrisome. Globally, death attributed to cardiovascular related disease is estimated at 19.1 million in 2020 (Tsao *et al.*, 2022). Research shows that hypertension is the commonest risk factor for cardiovascular disease (CVD) and leading cause of mortality worldwide. According to Joint National Committee (JNC) on prevention, detection, evaluation, and treatment of High Blood Pressure, hypertension is the elevation of systolic blood pressure (SBP) >179 mmHg or diastolic blood pressure (DBP) >109 mmHg (Adeloye *et al.*, 2021). It is estimated that about 10 million people die of hypertension every year (Chaturvedi *et al.*, 2024). Hypertension prevalence varies between countries and region. For example, few decades ago, high income countries (HICs) had decrease in hypertension prevalence while low and middle-income countries (LMICs) had significant increase. The significant increase in LMICs may be attributed to challenges in the healthcare system. In Mills *et al.* (2020), it is estimated that out of the total number of people living with hypertension, about 1.04 billion lived in LMICs while only 322 million lived in HICs. This statistic indicates that there is absolute burden of hypertension in LMICs. Thus there is need for a system that helps to monitor patient's health in a bid to curb the menace in LMICs.

Specifically, hypertension is the main risk factor for all kind of stroke, and coronary artery disease. More importantly, people with hypertension are prone to renal failure, heart failure, peripheral vascular disease, and other medical conditions (Manosroi and Williams, 2018). Though, Song *et al.* (2019) suggests hypertension in adulthood is associated with childhood hypertension, hypertension prevalence increase with age and sex. Also, other studies reveal that ethnicity and race can also play a major factor in hypertension prevalence. For example, a survey conducted by National Health and Nutrition Examination Survey (NHANES) 2005-2006 reveals that there is significant higher age-standardised prevalence of hypertension in non-Hispanic Black individuals (57.3%) than in non-Hispanic White individuals (43.8%) and Hispanic-Americans (44.7%) (Manosroi and Williams, 2018). It is important to note that hypertension is asymptomatic especially at the early stage and because of the asymptomatic nature of hypertension, there is need for routine and accurate blood pressure screening (Kitt *et al.*, 2019).

A hypertensive emergency is an elevation in blood pressure higher than the normal threshold that the symptoms are linked with signs of organ damage. The patient with severe worsening of organ function will need emergency care to decrease the blood pressure. Lowering of high blood pressure is expected to take place within the period of 1 to 2 hours (William and Schick, 2021). World Health Assembly (WHA) 72 resolution define emergency care as “an integrated platform for delivering accessible, quality, time-sensitive health care services for acute illness and injury across the life course” (Kannan *et al.*, 2020). In the case of a hypertension emergency, there is need for a risk-stratification tool that will help in the timely recognition of high-risk patients (Momtazmanesh *et al.*, 2020). Risk stratification is the process of estimating patient’s risk of an undesirable outcome especially when he or she

is presented to a hospital with symptoms of a particular illness. This involved categorising patients risk levels using risk factors. The aim of risk stratification is to plan for preventive strategies especially for high risk patient (Myers, 2020).

Continuous monitoring of blood pressure is vital to cardiovascular disease prevention and diagnosis (Li *et al.*, 2020). More importantly it prevent hypertension emergency. Conventional blood pressure measurement devices are based on the inflatable cuff-based technology. Some of the limitations of these devices are that it is inconvenient and uncomfortable and the periodic interrupts of the blood flow caused by cuff-based devices limits the blood pressure monitoring to intermittent measurement (Tsuyoshi, 2019). With the advent of IoT technology especially in the field of healthcare, there is a shift from measuring blood pressure without compressing the artery with an inflatable curve. IoT technology has enabled the measurement of blood pressure in a quick and continued manner in such a way that the status of blood pressure can be determined at intervals or throughout the day.

Blood pressure diagnosis and treatment are determined based on evidence available. This can be achieved through the use of personalised approach. Personalised diagnosis in this context requires the identification of specific genetic factors as well as environmental influences that precede the diagnosis of hypertension. Basically, healthcare system and provider's judgment and recommendations to patients are based on individual health conditions representing different abilities of disease control such as hypertension. Therefore, the classification of hypertension controllability among individuals is important for providing proper recommendations (Chaising *et al.*, 2021). Also, hypertension risk levels are stratified from various types of patient data, including demographics, medical history, physiological signals, and laboratory findings, which are all combined to yield a risk score

(Myers, 2020). This approach requires combining different variables to make decision. The holistic application of this approach is cumbersome for health professionals and increase waiting time for patient especially in LMICs where inadequate healthcare facility is a challenge. The emerging trend is the use of machine learning models and IoT to make prediction using many clinical characteristics mined from the electronic records (Melville *et al.*, 2020) and the use of IoT for data transfer from one device to another.

Monitoring, managing, and analysing medical reports become easier with the integration of decision making models with IoT devices. The emergence of (IoT) raised the opportunity of healthcare researchers to improve patient monitoring in a remote manner i.e. (home, hospital, and outdoors). Today, technology has enabled clinicians and family members to receive instant alerts/messages about the health information of their patients on a Smartphone, tablet, laptop, personal digital assistant (PDA), or personal computer (PC). The first set of clinical examinations is an evaluation of the vital signs of the patient (Sapra *et al.*, 2023). Modern IoT medical devices such as sensors and wearable devices are capable of collecting and transmitting data to a remote server for decision process (Sinclair, 2017). With advanced computing technology, complex issues like error and cost are minimised (Wang *et al.*, 2021). This study presents the development of a remote hypertension monitoring and risk stratification model.

There are significant limitations associated with existing remote hypertension risk stratification models, which this research seeks to address. One of the most important limitations is the issue of interpretability (Kolyskhina and Simoff, 2021). Many machine learning algorithms used in risk stratification model are adjudged to stratify correctly, but are often complex and difficult for healthcare professionals to understand their workability

and application in clinical settings (Ahmad *et al.*, 2018; Rudin *et al.*, 2021; Tonekaboni *et al.*, 2019). Lack of interpretability of such machine learning algorithm can affect the use of the model, as clinicians may be reluctant to rely on tools that do not provide clear reasoning for their risk assessment. The interpretability of a model is vital in clinical practice, as it allows healthcare providers to trust and effectively utilise the model's outputs in making informed decisions about patient care (Kolyshkina and Simoff, 2021) .

Another important limitation of existing models is their failure to adequately capture the complexity of modelling hypertension risk stratification as a multi-criteria decision problem (Montani and Striani, 2019; Omidvar *et al.*, 2018). Hypertension occurrence can be attributed to numerous factors, including age, gender, lifestyle, and comorbid conditions (Kuneinen, 2024). Traditional models often oversimplify this complexity, failing to integrate the full range of relevant hypertension risk factors into their risk assessments. This can lead to inaccurate stratification and inadequate management of patients, particularly in varied populations where different factors may have varying degrees of importance. By not accounting for the multifactorial nature of hypertension, existing models may miss important patient risk profiles, resulting in less effective interventions.

This study focuses on addressing these critical issues by developing a remote hypertension monitoring and risk stratification model utilising percentile rank-based multi-criteria decision making (PRBMCDM) algorithm. This model aims to integrate various health parameters to provide an accurate and timely assessment of hypertension risk levels by utilising a multi-criteria decision-making approach, the model can accommodate diverse

hypertension risk factors that influence hypertension, offering accurate and precise risk stratification. This method is useful in diverse populations, where individual factor may have different levels of importance in determining hypertension risk.

1.2 Motivation

The multifaceted usage of the mobile health system will help to address key issues and challenges in the area of healthcare-related costs in LMICs. The economic state of LMICs specifically Nigeria has changed the pattern of CVDs. The diagnosis and treatment of cardiovascular disease come at a price. The world bank estimated that about 53.5 % of the population earn less than \$1.90 a day (Ike and Onyema, 2020). This figure shows that Nigerians who live below the poverty line would not be able to access nor afford cardiovascular and other health-care services.

The increasing population of CVD patients in LMIC especially Nigeria is alarming. The World Health Organisation (WHO) in 2016 revealed that in Nigeria, non-communicable diseases were estimated to account for 29% of all deaths, of which CVDs contributed 11%. CVDs which have been found to be on the increase over the past 20 years in Nigeria include hypertension, heart failure, and stroke {Formatting Citation}. Result of research conducted by Internet World Statistics in 2017 shows that Nigeria has the highest mobile internet users in Africa with 48.4 to 93.5 million users between 2012 and 2017 respectively (Ayisat *et al.*, 2017). With the mobile internet growth, there is great potential for the use of mobile health for hypertension management in Nigeria and other LMICs as mobile phone ownership is high and growing rapidly, even among the poor (Melville *et al.*, 2020).

1.3 Statement of the Research Problem

Over the decades, there is a growing burden of non-communicable disease (NCD) in low and middle income countries (LMIC) with hypertension as one of the prevalent disease (NHS, 2020). A hypertensive emergency is the rise in blood pressure and the symptom is linked with signs of organ damage. Such patient requires emergency care to decrease the blood pressure within the period of 1 to 2 hours (William and Schick, 2021). Nigeria is not left out of this menace due to ill-fated and staggering healthcare system (NHS, 2020) . As a result, Nigerians bears a heavy burden of organ damage and sudden death before arrival at healthcare centres. One way to overcome these challenges is the provision of a sustainable health care system.

In the prevention of hypertension emergency, absolute hypertension risk assessment is a crucial element recommended for use across the globe (Unger *et al.*, 2020). This will enable high risk patients to be attended to within a time frame to avoid organ damage and death. Predicting hypertension risk status is mostly determined based on the evidence at hand. This can be achieved through the use of a personalised approach. Personalisation in this context requires the identification of the patient's genetic factors, environmental influences, lifestyle, and demographic data that precede the diagnosis of hypertension risk status (Dontje, 2019). Therefore, the classification of hypertension risk factors among individuals is crucial for providing proper recommendations (Chaising *et al.*, 2021). This approach is cumbersome for health professionals to bring together different variables to make such important and sensitive decisions. This process is time-consuming, leading to increased waiting times for patients, particularly in Nigeria, where limited healthcare facilities and a shortage of medical

personnel pose significant challenges. The use of decision making algorithms will help in this regard.

IoT technology has enabled the measurement of blood pressure in a quick, and continuous manner in such a way that the status of blood pressure can be determined at intervals or throughout the day. Monitoring, managing, and analysing disease becomes easier when decision making algorithm and IoT are integrated. The emergence of IoT raised the opportunity for healthcare researchers to improve patients monitoring in a remote manner. However, existing remote hypertension monitoring and risk stratification models are often limited by their complexity and lack of interpretability (Ahmad *et al.*, 2018; Rudin *et al.*, 2021; Tonekaboni *et al.*, 2019). While these advanced algorithms may provide accurate assessments, their complexity can prevent healthcare providers from fully understanding and trusting their outputs, thus hindering their practical application in clinical settings (Kolyshkina and Simoff, 2021). Additionally, these models often fail to adequately account for the multifactorial nature of hypertension, oversimplifying the condition and leading to inaccurate risk assessments (Montani and Striani, 2019; Omidvar *et al.*, 2018). This can result in inappropriate or ineffective interventions, especially in diverse patient's population where risk factors may vary significantly. Addressing these challenges requires an interpretable and comprehensive risk stratification model that integrates the complex, multifactorial influences on hypertension. This study is aimed at creating such model that will improve patient outcomes through more precise, actionable, and clinically relevant risk assessments.

1.4 Aim and Objectives of the Study

The aim of this study is to develop a remote hypertension monitoring and risk stratification model. The specific objectives are to:

- i. Determine and prioritise key hypertension risk factors
- ii. Design hypertension risk stratification model.
- iii. Implement/simulate the designed model
- iv. Evaluate the model performance.

1.5 Significance of the Study

This study centres on healthcare delivery relevant to hypertension that is beneficial to patients and providers with the help of advanced technology to collect hypertension data outside of traditional healthcare settings. This study is crucial especially in providing patients and professionals with a chance to intervene more promptly and prevent a manageable condition from becoming a health emergency that may require hospitalisation.

Given the health challenges prevalent in low- and middle-income countries (LMICs), this study addresses critical issues of accessibility, distance, and awareness that hinder hypertensive patients from regular monitoring and consistent blood pressure measurement. By enabling remote and personalised hypertension monitoring, the model empowers patients to actively manage their condition without relying solely on visits to healthcare professionals. Additionally, this approach offers a cost-effective hypertension management strategy for both patients and healthcare providers. It shifts the focus of care to home

settings, significantly reducing the need for expensive inpatient hypertension services and overall healthcare costs.

1.6 Scope and Limitation of the Study

The study is based on the following concepts: remote hypertension monitoring, classification of blood pressure threshold values, and hypertension risk stratification using PRBMCDM. These concepts are interrelated and interconnected. Moreover, this research investigates various methodologies to justify the proposed remote hypertension monitoring and risk stratification model. The research evaluates the performance of the proposed model. The research has some limitations. The implementation and scalability of the model may be hindered by resource constraints, especially in remote or underdeveloped regions with limited technological infrastructure. Also, real-world adoption may face challenges from technological barriers, such as inadequate internet connectivity or the lack of essential hardware for remote monitoring.

1.7 Thesis Outline

Chapter One: Introduction. This chapter presents the background to the study, the motivation for the study, statement of the problem, aim and objectives of the study and significance of the study, among other things.

Chapter Two: Literature Review. This chapter begins by exploring the global impact of hypertension, its causes, and associated risk factors, alongside diagnostic and monitoring techniques. It further delves into health monitoring systems, discussing their applications in various settings and the technologies involved, such as IoT and wearable devices. This

chapter also reviews existing remote monitoring systems for hypertension and their integration with telemedicine, identifying limitations in current technologies. Finally, it examines risk stratification models, comparing traditional methods with machine learning approaches and assessing their effectiveness in managing hypertension.

Chapter Three: Methodology. This chapter outlines the research design, emphasising methods for identifying and prioritising risk factors and techniques for data collection in remote monitoring systems are discussed. It then details the design of hypertension risk stratification model. The chapter concludes with criteria for evaluating model performance, using real-world hypertension data for validation.

Chapter Four: Results and Discussion. This chapter describes the implementation process of the proposed model, integrating it into healthcare settings. This is followed by a presentation of the results from the model evaluation. Also a comparative analysis of the PRBMCDM model against existing models is presented. The chapter also interprets the results, focusing on the model's effectiveness and accuracy, and lay the findings within the context of existing research.

Chapter Five: Conclusion and Recommendations. The conclusion summarises the key findings and reflections on the study's aim and objectives, while the recommendations suggest future research directions and the possibility of applying the model in other different healthcare settings.

CHAPTER TWO

2.0

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Overview of Hypertension

Hypertension, also referred to as high blood pressure (HBP) simply means the pressure in the arteries is higher than it should be (William and Schick, 2021). According to Unger *et al.* (2020), hypertension is “when a person’s systolic blood pressure (SBP) in the office or clinic is ≥ 140 mm Hg and/or their diastolic blood pressure (DBP) is ≥ 90 mm Hg following repeated examinations. Hypertension is one of the strongest risk factors for nearly all different CVD acquired during a lifetime (Kjeldsen, 2018). Hypertension can be classified into two types;

- i. primary hypertension (Manosroi and Williams, 2018), is considered a set of symptoms and not a disease, with the individual diseases having a common sign of elevated blood pressure.
- ii. Secondary hypertension (Charles *et al.*, 2017), is the “type of hypertension with an underlying and potentially reversible cause. It makes up only a small fraction (5% to 10%) of hypertensive cases”.

The American College of Cardiology/American Heart Association (ACC/AHA) Hypertension Guideline (Carey and Whelton, 2018) provides accurate measurement of BP, stressing increased use of out-of-office measurements to confirm hypertension and to detect white coats and masked hypertension. The guidelines modify stage 1 hypertension BP threshold value range is from 130 to 139/80 to 89 mm Hg compared with 140 to 159/90 to 99 mm Hg in JNC 7, and stage 2 hypertension BP threshold value range is from 140/90 mm Hg or higher versus 160/100 mm Hg or higher in JNC 7. However, the “pre hypertension”

category in JNC 7 (SBP of 120 to 129 mm Hg and DBP <80 mm Hg) was replaced with the term “elevated BP” to convey the increased CVD risk compared with normal BP (<120/80 mm Hg). Classification of blood pressure for adults is presented in Table 2.1.

Table 2.1: Blood pressure classification for adults ≥18 years (Carey and Whelton, 2018)

Class	SBP (mmHg)		DBP (mmHg)
Normal	Less 120	and	80
Elevated	120-129	<i>And</i>	Less 80
Stage1(Moderate high)	130-139	<i>or</i>	80-89
Stage 2 (High)	140	<i>or</i>	90
Hypertensive crisis	180	and/or	120

Varounis *et al.* (2017) divide Hypertensive crises into two: when target organ damage is absent, the hypertensive crisis is referred to as hypertensive urgencies. However, when there is a presence of acute target organ damage then it is referred to as hypertensive emergencies. ACC/AHA 2017 defined hypertensive crises as the elevation of systolic blood pressure (SBP) >180 mmHg or diastolic blood pressure (DBP) > 120 mmHg.

2.1.1 Causes of hypertension

The root of hypertension cannot be precisely defined because it is a sign and is most likely to have many causes. An apnea (Javaheri *et al.*, 2017) is the malfunctioning of aspiratory airflow for up to ten seconds. It is the reduction of airflow that persisted for a maximum of ten seconds or beyond and is linked with a drop in arterial oxyhemoglobin saturation and or

electroencephalographic arousal. The following are summary of identifiable causes of hypertension (Oussama and Mohammed, 2005)

- i. Sleep apnea
- ii. Primary aldosteronism
- iii. Thyroid or parathyroid disease
- iv. Chronic steroid therapy
- v. Renovascular complications
- vi. Chronic kidney disease
- vii. Drug-induced or related causes
- viii. Pheochromocytoma

Hypertension is not just a risk factor for CVDs but it is also an asymptomatic condition with its own risk factors (Molla *et al.*, 2021). Pulungan *et al.* (2022) identified hypertension risk factors among women in Indonesia to include: alcohol consumption, age, level of education, smoking behaviour, underweight BMI, contraception use, unhealthy food consumption, fat-based BMI and stress. Also, another study conducted for elderly in Indonesia identified similar risk factors (Oktaviyani *et al.*, 2022). Global epidemiology study (Mills *et al.*, 2020) identified high sodium intake, low potassium intake, lack of physical activities, overweight and obesity, un healthy diet as a potential risk factors for hypertension. Several researches such as Ibebuike *et al.* (2021); and Sanya and Ikhifa, (2020) were conducted in Nigeria to identify hypertension risk factors and its prevalence.

2.1.2 Diagnosis of hypertension

The Hypertension Practice Guidelines provided by ISH 2020 in Unger *et al.* (2020) is presented in Table 2.2.

Table 2.2 Recommendations for office blood pressure measurement

Conditions	Conduct measurements in a quiet comfortable atmosphere. Avoid alcohol, and exercise for at least 30 minutes prior; empty the bladder; Sit and relax for 3–5 minutes before taking measurements. Ensure silence by both patient and staff within the period of measurements.
Positions	Patient should ensure the Arm should rest on a table. The arm to be within the chest level.; patient should rest on a chair.
Device	The use of a upper-arm cuff device is recommended.
Curve	calibrated manual auscultatory device may be used as alternative. The inflatable bladder cuff of the device should cover at least 75%–100% of the arm circumference...
Protocol	three measurements should be taking to ensuring a one-minute interval between each.. use average of the last two readings.
Interpretation	BP readings of $\geq 140/90$ mm Hg on 2–3 office visits are indicative of hypertension.

2.1.3 Evaluation of hypertensive patients

Hypertensive Patients are mostly asymptomatic; however, there are underlying conditions that can suggest elevated and severe hypertension that require further investigation. Unger *et al.* (2020) suggests the following clinical tests:

- i. *Physical examination:* The physical examination for hypertension includes assessing blood circulation and the heart.
- ii. *Laboratory Investigations and ECG:* Laboratory investigations include blood tests as well as a dipstick urine test. A 12-lead ECG test is also recommended.

Also, Unger *et al.* (2020) provided a classification mechanism for other risk factors such as hypertension-mediated Organ Damage (HMOD), and previous disease as presented in Table 2.3.

Table 2.3: Classification of a simplified hypertension risk according to additional risk factors

Risk Factors HMOD and Disease	High-Normal 130–139/ 85–89	Grade 1 140–159/ 90–99	Grade 2 ≥160/ ≥100
without risk factors	Low	Low	Moderate High
One or two risk factors	Low	Moderate	High
3 or above risk factors	Low Moderate	High	High
MOD, CVD grade 3, diabetes, CVD	High	High	High

2.1.4 Evaluation for hypertensive crisis

Hypertensive emergency is usually linked with elevated BP with acute HMOD. This type of hypertension can rapidly damage organs such as the retina, heart, large arteries, brain and kidneys. (Unger *et al.*,2020). A hypertensive crisis is divided into two: hypertension urgencies and hypertension emergencies depend on their effect on the target organ. Both

have different clinical management and time frame for an intervention. However, both need quick intervention to lessen complication and death of the patients. More specifically, hypertension urgencies require attention within 24–48 hours of occurrence while hypertension emergency requires attention within 1-2 hours (Varounis *et al.*, 2017).

2.1.5 Hypertension measuring techniques

Over the years, there are numerous ways to measure blood pressure. One approach is the office BPM (Dontje, 2019). This method involves the use of manual or automated sphygmomanometer mostly used by health professionals. The ACC/AHA hypertension Guideline (Carey and Whelton, 2018) proposed that two or more blood pressure measurements be taken on two occasions before arriving at the diagnosis of hypertension using the average of the measurements.

Another method was proposed by Canadian Hypertension Education Program Guidelines (Dontje, 2019) which recommends automated office blood pressure (AOBP). The use of AOBP requires a specialised device that involves taking reading of the patient's blood pressure for five consecutive times within a defined interval. This procedure will reduce the incidence of white coat hypertension (Dontje, 2019). This method is not common in LMIC especially Nigeria.

The last measuring method for BP is ambulatory blood pressure monitoring (ABPM). This method involves the use of mobile technology where a patient wears a blood pressure cuff-like device on the arm while doing his regular activities. The monitor takes the measurement on schedule basis (Dontje, 2019).

2.2 Taxonomy of Remote Monitoring System

Over the last decades, researchers have proposed different techniques used in the area of remote monitoring systems (Rajeswari *et al.*, 2021). Evidence from existing literature has proven that classifying and analysing these systems into groups of interrelated works is a difficult task. This section attempt to group research works related to remote health monitoring systems that share common attributes, features, and characteristics. Figure 2.1 presents remote monitoring systems divided into three main groups. These groups include remote health monitoring context for which remote monitoring systems are developed, remote monitoring technologies are devices that characterise the developed systems, remote monitoring services for which the proposed systems were implemented.

Figure 2.1: Remote monitoring grouping (Serhani *et al.*, 2020)

2.2.1 Remote monitoring context

2.2.1.1 Home-based remote monitoring system

Home-based remote monitoring systems are widely employed to support elderly individuals, stroke survivors, and diabetic patients by enabling consistent health surveillance and assistance within their homes. Home-based remote monitoring system reduces the burden of frequent visit to the hospital. This is helpful in LMIC where geographical distances, transportation challenges and overcrowding in outpatient departments are a major challenge. Numerous studies have been conducted on home-based remote monitoring systems. For example, Chatrati *et al.* (2020) proposed a smart system that measures blood glucose and blood pressure, predicts diabetes status, and promptly alerts healthcare providers in case of abnormalities. Similar system was developed for diabetic patient called Home-Based Rehabilitation (HBR) system (Chae *et al.* 2020). The system utilises smartwatches and smartphones for the detection of log rehabilitation exercises, ensuring strict compliance to prescribed drugs. Wearable devices were used in Wazir *et al.* (2020) to monitor the compliance of therapies like Optimal Lymph Flow (TOLF) from the home to improve patient wellbeing and adequacy of treatment. During COVID-19 home-based monitoring systems were used for monitoring the well being of patients from their home (Izdrui *et al.*, 2021).

2.2.1.2 Hospital-based remote monitoring systems

Hospital-based remote monitoring systems are designed to be used in the hospital setting. The goal of hospital-based remote monitoring system is to deliver care and manage clinical activities in the hospital setting. Hospital-based monitoring system can be used in different

unit of hospital such as the intensive care unit, outpatient department, and maternity wards. One of the benefits of deploying a hospital-based remote monitoring system is provision of convenient environment for medical team to monitor vital parameters of a patient who is on admission or within the hospital environment in real-time (Kaieski *et al.*, 2020). Such a system can also be designed and deployed to monitor the hospital's assets. For example, Prasad *et al.* (2020) developed an android-based device for monitoring patients in a hospital environment. The proposed system was designed to enable secured data flow between the patient and the doctor.

2.2.2 Remote monitoring technologies

2.2.2.1 Enabling technology

IOT-based monitoring system: IoT has increasingly been used in different industries and more IoT devices are coming up almost on daily basis (Mohammed *et al.*, 2020). IoT is the collection of connected devices on the Internet using information sensing equipment to perform smart recognition, positioning, tracking, monitoring, and administration (Mohammed *et al.*, 2020). In the health industry, it is necessary to analyse time-sensitive data in a real-time manner, especially real-time sensitive diseases such as cardiac disorder, respiratory disease, and blood pressure (Abdulmalek *et al.*, 2022). In a smart a city, IoT is the main front-end with multiple interconnected networks of sensors. Most importantly, the integration of Radio Frequency Identification tags (RFID) and Wireless Sensor Networks (WSNs) are very suitable for identification and tracking of patients (Krishna *et al.*, 2021).

Fog/Edge IOT monitoring system: Relying on traditional cloud architecture may not be appropriate for some kinds of health situations. The fog/edge computing approach is more suitable because of its special feature of computing, storage, and network connectivity. For example, Dilibal (2020) presents the development of smart healthcare monitoring platforms using edge-IoMT computing architecture. Similarly, Fernández-Caramés *et al.* (2019) used Fog-based Smartphone to collect data from the CGMs and transmit them to a remote cloud/blockchain. Also, Gaitan and Ungurean (2019) used Edge/Fog Computing layers to process data from the mobile device. In Ben *et al.* (2020), mobile application is employed to play the role of the Fog server which view and analyse the environmental parameters of the hospitalisation room remotely, monitoring of health parameters by nurses and preparing a medical report. IoT-based fog monitoring system was used to monitor BP and to diagnose the stage of hypertension remotely in Sood and Mahajan (2019).

2.2.3 Monitoring devices

2.2.3.1 Mobile devices

Mobile devices are used within and outside the hospital by patients and physicians. Such mobile devices include mobile phones, smart devices, android, and pocket PC. These devices can be used either as data processing station or as a working module. Mobile device is effective in disease monitoring such as hypertension risk monitoring. (Cechetti *et al.*, 2019; de Marchi *et al.*, 2020; Egejuru *et al.*, 2019). Mobile device is also used in the area of stroke aftercare management (Kim *et al.*, 2020; Fell *et al.* 2019; Seah *et al.* 2019). Mobile device is used in Fernández-Caramés *et al.* (2019) to enhance Continuous Glucose Monitoring (CGM). Also, Oleari *et al.* (2019) designed a multi-component platform used with knowledge-based Artificial Intelligence for children/pre-adolescents to obtain data for

Type One Diabetes Mellitus (T1DM) like glucose values, insulin doses, carbohydrates' intake) and other activities (sports and emotions) to monitor patient. Bellei *et al.* (2020) developed a health application called Soins DM for monitoring the treatment of type 1 diabetes mellitus using interactive data visualization approach.

A remote triage system is very important and helps in pre-hospital emergencies. Marchiori *et al.* (2020) developed a triage system that uses mobile phone to evaluate types of care through interactions with patients. Li *et al.* (2021) proposed a dynamic-based system that monitors patient health indexes using mobile terminal. The proposed system framework consists of acquisition of various physiological indexes, wireless communication, display unit using mobile terminal, and disease alarm.

2.2.3.2 Wearable remote monitoring systems

Some research works integrate wearable devices into remote monitoring systems. The wearable device is used either in the home settings to monitor different vital signs, in the hospital settings, like the ICU and non-ICU, or in the ambulatory settings. Most of the wearable devices are worn on different parts of the body. Such wearable devices include an electromyogram (EMG) patch system that can be worn on the lower leg, to detect real-time muscle fatigue during physical exercise (Liu *et al.* 2019), Foot wearable devices used to monitor Parkinson's disease, diabetes, and various disorders (Drăgulinescu *et al.*, 2020). A similar device known as SWEET Sock (Amitrano *et al.*,2020) is used for gait and postural assessment.

Chung *et al.* (2021) developed a posture correction device that comprises smart necklace, notebook computer, and smartphone. Assisting Elders At Home (ANGELAH) is a system capable of integrating monitoring and emergency detection subsystem with networking subsystem. Similar wearable emergency detection device was developed in Taleb *et al.* (2019). Chae *et al.* (2020) proposed a web based wearable rehabilitation system to evaluate upper limb of a stroke survivor using smart watch and machine learning model. Kerr *et al.* (2021) proposed a fuzzy triage system using visual, and tactile sensing, integrated into a robot to accurately measure key vital signs in humans.

2.2.3.3 Sensing Devices

Sensing devices are the hub of the health monitoring system. Virtually all monitoring technologies (enabling technology and monitoring devices) integrate sensing devices which take the centre stage in receiving biomedical signals and forward them it to the edge or fog layer for processing or visualization. However, this study categorises research that focuses solely on health monitoring of vital signs using a combination of vital signs and environmental sensors. Among these research initiatives are: Yeh *et al.*(2019) who proposed a visual reality stroke rehabilitation system using kinect technology. The task of the system is to recover the function of the upper extremity and Ahmed *et al.* (2020) designed a system that incorporate biomedical sensor to detect critical health data such as BP, ECG, EEG and SpO₂ using time criticality based decision making algorithm (TCDMA). Table 2.4 presents some selected sensors used for vital sign monitoring.

Table 2.4: Selected sensors used for vital sign monitoring (Atabo *et al.*, 2023)

Sensing Technology	Usage	Application
BP sensor	BP measurement	Hypertension
BG sensor	BG measurement	Diabetes
inertial measurement unit (IMU) sensor	human activity recognition	Stroke rehabilitation
pulse sensor	Heart rate variability	Hypertension
Pendant sensor	Optimal lymph flow	Lymphedema
EKG signals sensor	Electrocardiograph measurement	Cardiac
ECG sensor	heart electrical activity measurement	Heart disease
EMG sensor	Determine the muscle-fatigue conditions	Muscle fatigue

2.2.4 Health monitoring system services

In the literature, health monitoring systems are developed for certain purposes and targets. These purposes are referred to as services in this thesis. A service-based system aims to perform the job of a health professional using a specific or a combination of machine learning algorithm. This thesis classifies the service-based health monitoring systems into four main categories: prediction, diagnosis, classification, and activity. Selected papers on service-based health monitoring systems are presented in the Table 2.5.

Table 2.5: Service-based health monitoring system (Atabo *et al.*, 2023)

Papers	Service-based	Algorithm	Application
Akhbarifar <i>et al.</i> (2023)	Diagnosis	K-star classification	Hypertension
Chatrati <i>et al.</i> (2020)	Prediction	SVM, k-NN, DT, LR, DA	Diabetes and Hypertension
Chae <i>et al.</i> (2020)	Activity	CNN	Stroke
Souri <i>et al.</i> (2020)	Diagnosis	DT, RF, SVM, MLP	Student health
Egejuru <i>et al.</i> (2019)	Classification	Adaptive Neuro-Fuzzy Inference System	Hypertension
Amitrano <i>et al.</i> (2020)	Diagnosis	Passing–Bablok regression, Bland–Altman analysis	Posture
Iranpak (2021)	Diagnosis	LSTM deep neural network	General health
Nath and Thapliyal (2021)	Diagnosis	MLP , DT AdaBoost	Elderly
Priyadharsan <i>et al.</i> (2019)	Prediction	KNN classifier	General health
Hao (2022)	Activity	neural network	Sport
Alazzam <i>et al.</i> (2021)	Diagnosis	decision tree algorithm	General health

2.2.5 Existing remote monitoring systems for hypertension

2.2.5.1 Wearable and portable devices

Blood Pressure Monitoring Devices such as the Omron Evolv (Golbus *et al.*, 2021), Withings BPM Connect (Tasić *et al.*, 2022), and QardioArm (Mazoteras-Pardo *et al.*, 2020) are widely used for at-home blood pressure monitoring. These devices are often wireless, compact, and easy to use, allowing patients to take measurements at their convenience. Smartwatches and Wearable devices like the Omron HeartGuide (Liang and Chapa-Martell, 2021) and Samsung Galaxy Watch (Rho *et al.*, 2024) integrate blood pressure monitoring

capabilities with other health metrics like heart rate and activity levels. These wearables are designed for continuous monitoring, providing real-time data on the go.

2.2.5.2 Mobile applications

Some brand of mobile applications simultaneously performs the task of tracking data and analysing it in real-time. Mobile apps such as Omron Connect and Withings Health Mate synchronise with BP monitoring device to track readings, analyse trends, and offer recommendations (Tasić *et al.*, 2022). These applications often encourage patient engagement by providing educational content, lifestyle tips, and medication reminders. This helps improve adherence to treatment plans and promotes better self-management.

2.2.5.3 Cloud platforms and data management

Cloud platforms like Apple Health, Google Fit, and Microsoft HealthVault allow patients to store their BP data in the cloud, making it accessible to multiple devices. These platforms also enable long-term trend analysis and integration with other health data (Machorro-Cano *et al.*, 2024). Cloud platforms facilitate data sharing with care giver, allowing monitoring in a remote and real-time manner. Systems like Vivify Health and Biofourmis offer comprehensive remote monitoring solutions that include hypertension management (Sun and Zhou, 2023; Yadav, 2024).

2.2.5.4 Telemedicine integration

Telemedicine integration enables remote consultations. Telemedicine platforms such as Teladoc (Al Baalharith *et al.*, 2022) and Amwell (Power, 2020) enable the sharing of patients BP data with healthcare providers during virtual consultations. This integration

enhances the ability to regulate treatment plans in real-time according to current BP readings. Some systems, like Philips eCareCoordinator, provide continuous remote monitoring services, alerting healthcare providers of any significant changes in the patient's BP that may require immediate attention (Naqvi *et al.*, 2023).

2.3 Risk Stratification Model Development

The integration of IoT with machine learning algorithms has revitalised patients' healthcare management. The use of patients health records whether electronic or hospital case files when harnessed and analysed provide an opportunity for health professionals and government an opportunity to make clinical decisions and use them for risk evaluation. For quite some time, few types of research related to risk stratification were carried out using definite strategies where patients are grouped based on the risk levels, using multiple risk factors related to the disease. Risk stratification is a tool that helps in the identification of patients at different risk levels. This will enable health professionals to predict and estimate resources that will be required by the patients.

Modelling risk stratification involves rigorous process to identify clinical and demographical pointers for predicting and assessing disease risk levels. Evidence from the literature reveals that there are no specific risk stratification tools for a specific disease condition that can be applied to all patients. Rather, many developed new models, while others attempt to improve on the existing model (Douglas *et al.*, 2019; Xie *et al.*, 2021). Risk stratification tools are developed using biological indicators. prospective risk factor candidates can be collected from electronic health records (Haimovich *et al.*, 2020; Lyon *et al.*, 2022), data sources acquired during clinical studies (Chu *et al.*, 2021), data collection

through interviews (Zheng *et al.*, 2023) and data from the existing risk score (Kanwar *et al.*, 2020).

The initial step in risk factor candidates selection is to split the patients into two groups (the presence or absence of a medical condition) using clinical guidelines like ESC/ESH (Do *et al.*, 2020) and risk factors measurement (Molla *et al.*, 2021). The Identification of risk factors can be evaluated (Sandqvist *et al.*, 2021) or compared with other risk scores to ascertain the statistically significant difference between the group of risk factors (Manreet *et al.*, 2020). Risk factors can take the form of continuous or categorical variables. Such variables are expressed as mean \pm standard deviation (Ting-Wei and Shien-Fong, 2020), median and interquartile range (Alemayehu *et al.*, 2019). Continuous variables can also be measured in percentage (Martínez *et al.*, 2020). To test variance between variable groups, statistical testing can be used. Student t-test and Man-Whitney U-test for non-parametric variables can also be conducted (Haimovich *et al.*, 2020; Rosenkranz *et al.*, 2022; Zheng *et al.*, 2023), Wilcoxon rank sum test (Shen *et al.*, 2017). Chi-squared test (Bonnievie *et al.*, 2019; Lessmann *et al.*, 2021).

In categorical variables, risk factors are labelled and allocated to a group. Such values include gender, family history, smoking, high-salt diet, diabetes and physical activity (Zhao *et al.*, 2020). The values of the variables are allocated to a set of groups. The categorical variables can be expressed as percentages or numbers. The statistical significance of categorical variables can be tested using chi-squared (Kanwar *et al.*, 2020; Rosen *et al.*, 2023). To test secondary hypothesis in the categorical variable Fisher exact test can be used

(Arancibia *et al.*, 2018), The result of the statistical testing in both continuous and categorical variables reveals risk factors distribution between groups that indicate probable influence on clinical event or endpoints. Table 2.6 presents approaches to risk stratification.

Table 2.6 Risk stratification approaches

Disease	Motivation/Approaches	Papers
pulmonary arterial hypertension	Apply the existing risk score to predicts outcome in patients with comorbidities.	Rosenkranz <i>et al.</i> (2022)
chronic thromboembolic pulmonary hypertension cardiovascular risk	Applying the existing risk models to predicts survival Developed and validate a new model to predict retinal photographs	Sandqvist <i>et al.</i> (2021) Rim <i>et al.</i> (2021)
Hypertension	Cardiovascular Risk prediction	Castillo <i>et al.</i> (2022)
Cardiovascular	Using existing model to predic 3-month CV complications in elective major vascular surgical patients	Golubovic <i>et al.</i> (2018)
Cardiovascular	new representation of patient data for risk prediction	Ngufor <i>et al.</i> (2020)
Chest pain	New model to predict the risk of Major Adverse Cardiovascular Events (MACEs) in chest pain patients with NSTEMI-ACS. Methods	Zheng <i>et al.</i> (2023)
Cardiovascular	Using cardiovascular risk factors to design a risk calculator	Cuadrado-Godia <i>et al.</i> (2019)
Pulmonary arterial hypertension	Demonstrating the predictive ability of an existing model (REVEAL)	Manreet <i>et al.</i> (2020)

2.3.1 Methods and algorithms for risk stratification

Traditional methods of risk stratification

- i. Scoring Systems:* CHADS2 and CHA2DS2-VASc scores (Al-Radeef, 2019). In this model, the mechanism of risk stratification is by scoring system. These systems assign points to various risk factors and sum them to produce a score. The score corresponds to a risk level (low, moderate, high). The strength of this model lies in its simplicity, especially the usage, and can be quickly applied in clinical settings. However, the model may oversimplify complex risk profiles and fail to account for interactions between risk factors. The CHA₂DS₂-VASc score is static and does not account for changes in a patient's condition over time, potentially leading to outdated risk assessments.

- ii. Regression-based Models:* These models use logistic or Cox proportional hazards regression to estimate the relationship between various predictors such as cholesterol, blood pressure, age, and the outcome (Bislimovska and Minov, 2023). The output is the probability or hazard ratio indicating risk, providing estimate of risk and allows for the inclusion of multiple variables. This method requires assumptions about the linearity of relationships and may not perform well with non-linear or complex interactions. The Framingham Risk Score is a model that predicts ten years risk of cardiovascular events. Framingham model estimates the ten year risk, which may not be suitable for young adult that might have low short-term risk but significant lifetime risk.

2.3.1.1 Machine learning algorithms in risk stratification

i. Supervised learning models

Random Forests is a collection of decision trees that are trained on a random subset of the data (Surya *et al.*, 2023). The process is to divide the final prediction of all trees. This model is good in handling large number of predictors and complex interactions well; robust to overfitting. Though it is less interpretable than traditional regression models; it can also be computationally intensive (Aria *et al.*, 2021).

Support Vector Machine (SVM) is a model that finds the optimal hyperplane that separates different classes such as high risk vs. low risk in the feature space. It is efficient in high-dimensional spaces and with non-linear boundaries. One of the challenges of SVM is the selection of right kernel function (Lyon *et al.*, 2022). SVMs are not probabilistic, which can complicate risk interpretation.

Neural Network is a model that mimics the configuration of the human brain with layers of interconnected neurons (Surya *et al.*, 2023). It can model complex, non-linear relationships between inputs such as clinical measurements and outputs such as risk levels. It is extremely flexible and capable of capturing intricate patterns in data. However, this model requires large datasets and significant computational resources; often considered a "black box" due to difficulty in interpreting how the model makes decisions (Buhrmester *et al.*, 2021).

ii. *Unsupervised learning models*

Clustering Algorithm is used to classify patients into clusters based on some connection in the data, without predefined risk categories. For example, k-means clustering can identify subgroups of patients with similar risk profiles (Prajapati and Timalisin, 2022). This algorithm is very good at discovering hidden patterns in data that will enable the identification of novel risk categories. However, the choice of clusters (k) is often arbitrary and can significantly influence results.

Principal Component Analysis (PCA) is a model that reduces the dimensionality of data by transforming the original variables into a set of linearly uncorrelated components. These components can then be used in risk models (Anitha and Baghavathi Priya, 2019). The strength of this method is its ability to handle high-dimensional data and reduce noise. PCA can be challenging to interpret, and important information might be lost in the dimensionality reduction process.

2.3.1.2 Hybrid Models

A model might use logistic regression for baseline risk estimation and then refine predictions using machine learning techniques. In this method, traditional models provide a foundation, while machine learning adds layers of complexity to improve accuracy. This will improve balances interpretability with predictive power; leverages the strengths of both approaches (Maleckar *et al.*, 2021). However, some of these models are computationally complex to implement and require careful calibration to avoid overfitting.

Multiple prediction models such as SVMs, logistic regression, decision trees can be combined to produce a final prediction. Methods like bagging, boosting, and stacking are commonly used. This can significantly improve prediction accuracy and robustness by averaging out the biases of individual models. However, the complexity increases with the number of models and interpretability can be a challenge (Ming-Siang *et al.*, 2024).

2.3.2 Multi-criteria decision model and its application in health care

Multi-criteria Decision-Making (MCDM) models are a class of methodologies used to evaluate and prioritise multiple conflicting criteria in decision-making processes (Oketch-rabah *et al.*, 2021). These models are useful in complex scenarios, where decisions often involve trade-offs between various factors like cost, effectiveness, risk, and patient preferences. MCDM models can be broadly classified into two categories:

- i. *Compensatory models:* These models allow trade-offs between two criteria. Where a poor score in one criterion can be used to compensate a good score in another. Examples include the Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) and the Analytic Network Process (ANP) (Pownuk and Kreinovich, 2018).
- ii. *Non-Compensatory models:* In these models, trade-offs are not allowed. If an alternative fails to meet a certain criterion, it may be excluded regardless of its performance on other criteria. Examples include the Elimination by Aspects (EBA) and the Lexicographic method (Pownuk and Kreinovich, 2018).

2.3.2.1 Common MCDM models in healthcare

- i. *Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP)*: AHP is one of the most widely used MCDM methods. It involves structuring a decision problem into a hierarchy, comparing the elements at each level pairwise, and calculating a weighted score for each alternative (Citrawati *et al.*, 2020). AHP is used for determining the allocation of limited resources such as budget and medical staff, among competing needs. This model helps physicians and patients choose the most appropriate treatment by weighing factors such as efficacy, side effects, cost, and patient preferences. The model assists policymakers in evaluating and prioritising health interventions or programs.
- ii. *Analytic Network Process (ANP)*: ANP is an extension of AHP that allows for more complex interdependencies between criteria and alternatives. It uses a network structure rather than a hierarchy, accommodating feedback and interrelated elements (Taherdoost, 2023). ANP is useful in medical decision support by evaluating complex treatment plans where various medical conditions, treatments, and outcomes are interdependent. It is also useful in healthcare planning by analysing the interrelationships among different aspects of healthcare systems, such as patient care, hospital management, and policy-making.
- iii. *Technique for Order of Preference by Similarity to Ideal Solution (TOPSIS)*: TOPSIS ranks alternatives based on their distance from an ideal solution (best possible) and a negative ideal solution (worst possible) (Kumar and Kaur, 2023). The alternative closest to the ideal solution and furthest from the negative ideal is

preferred. TOPSIS is applied in risk assessment by prioritising patients based on risk levels for personalised care. It is also applied in hospital performance evaluation by assessing and ranking the performance of healthcare providers based on criteria like quality of care, efficiency, and patient satisfaction (Almahdi *et al.*, 2019).

- iv. *Multi-Attribute Utility Theory (MAUT)*: MAUT involves defining a utility function that captures the decision-makers preferences across different criteria. It then evaluates each alternative based on this utility function to determine the best option. MAUT is used in assessing different treatment options by integrating patient preferences and clinical outcomes into a utility score (Jiby *et al.*, 2022). Evaluating new medical technologies based on multiple factors like effectiveness, cost, and social impact.
- v. *Fuzzy MCDM*: Fuzzy MCDM incorporates fuzzy logic into traditional MCDM models to handle uncertainty and imprecision in decision-making (Taherdoost, 2023). It is particularly useful when criteria or preferences are not clear-cut. Fuzzy MCDM is used for addressing the uncertainty in medical diagnoses and treatment outcomes and evaluating patient satisfaction where responses may be subjective or ambiguous.

2.3.2.2 Application of MCDM models in healthcare

Application of MCDM in risk stratification: Traditional risk stratification models often rely on single-dimension scoring systems such as clinical risk scores, which may overlook

important factors due to their limited scope. MCDM, however, integrates various clinical, demographic, and behavioral factors to create a holistic view of patient risk (Taherdoost, 2023). Studies have shown that MCDM techniques such as the Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP), TOPSIS, and PROMETHEE can systematically evaluate multiple criteria, improving the precision and relevance of risk stratification models in healthcare settings (Frazão, 2018).

AHP can be used to assess hypertension risk by weighting factors such as age, blood pressure, and cholesterol levels. AHP is effective in creating clear priority rankings for patient risk categories (Drake *et al.*, 2017). A study by Sivakumar and Muthu (2020) demonstrated that TOPSIS could stratify patients with heart disease, identifying those at highest risk and allowing for tailored intervention strategies. PROMETHEE (Ranking Organization Method for Enrichment Evaluation) has been applied in stratifying complex cases with competing health factors. For example, (Almahdi *et al.*, 2019) found PROMETHEE particularly effective in balancing both quantitative and qualitative criteria, such as lifestyle factors and socioeconomic status, when assessing cardiovascular risk.

In CVD, MCDM methods such as AHP, TOPSIS, and PROMETHEE have been widely applied in risk stratification. Studies show these techniques can better capture comprehensive risk profiles, which include behavioural, genetic, and environmental factors (Zaidan *et al.*, 2017). MCDM can be used for diabetes patients (Kumar and Kaur, 2023) to identify risk level based on criteria such as blood sugar levels, lifestyle, and age. In Alamoodi and Dawood (2022), AHP was used to prioritise diabetic patients needing immediate intervention, achieving a more balanced, data-driven patient stratification

approach (Almahdi *et al.*, 2019). The use of AHP in oncology to prioritise treatment plans based on patient-specific factors, including tumor markers, treatment side effects, and patient preferences is promising. A study by Erol and Karadayi (2019) shows how MCDM can weigh such diverse factors, supporting clinicians in individualised cancer management

Application of MCDM in prioritisation of high-risk patients: Multi-Criteria Decision-Making (MCDM) methods are widely applied in healthcare to prioritise high-risk patients, helping streamline treatment prioritisation and resource allocation by systematically evaluating a variety of patient-specific factors. Techniques like Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) and TOPSIS assess multiple criteria such as vital signs, lab results, and patient demographics. MCDM has been shown to improve patient outcomes by identifying those at greatest risk more quickly (Salman *et al.*, 2017). For instance, AHP has been applied to prioritise trauma cases based on factors like injury severity and comorbidities, leading to more effective emergency interventions (Napi *et al.*, 2019).

Significant number of research on pandemics such as COVID-19 used MCDM models for stratifying high-risk populations based on infection risk, comorbidities, and other factors like vaccination status and exposure level. For example, TOPSIS and fuzzy AHP have been applied to prioritise COVID-19 patients for intensive care based on oxygen levels, age, and coexisting conditions. Studies in pandemic preparedness have shown that MCDM can aid in rapid patient prioritisation, particularly when healthcare resources are constrained, improving both survival rates and resource management (Alamoodi and Dawood, 2022).

Emerging applications of MCDM involve its integration with machine learning to continuously update patient priorities based on real-time data. This approach supports

dynamic prioritisation, adapting to changing patient conditions and potentially improving the predictive accuracy of risk assessments. Research by Malapane *et al.* (2022) has shown that such MCDM-based models are particularly effective for personalised patient monitoring, especially in intensive care or home care settings where patient conditions can change rapidly. By utilising MCDM for patient prioritisation, healthcare providers can make evidence-based, systematic decisions that enhance care for high-risk patients, ultimately leading to better outcomes and optimal use of medical resources.

Application of MCDM in hospital resource allocation: The application of Multi-Criteria Decision-Making (MCDM) in hospital resource allocation and operational efficiency has become essential for optimising healthcare services, especially in environments facing budget constraints, limited resources, and high patient demand. MCDM helps healthcare administrators evaluate various resource allocation options by balancing multiple factors, such as costs, patient needs, and clinical outcomes. MCDM methods, such as AHP and TOPSIS, are widely used to optimise hospital staffing, ensuring that there are enough healthcare professionals across departments based on patient volume, severity of cases, and peak hours (Lin *et al.*, 2021). Studies demonstrate that MCDM can evaluate and balance criteria like costs, patient demand, staff expertise, and availability, resulting in improved staffing efficiency and patient satisfaction.

In critical care and emergency settings, hospitals often face a shortage of equipment and beds, making MCDM valuable for prioritising their allocation. MCDM approaches can help decision-makers evaluate which patients should receive priority for beds or access to

equipment like ventilators. By factoring in patient severity, potential outcomes, and resource availability, hospitals can improve patient care and reduce wait times (Algfari *et al.*, 2022) .

Application of MCDM in epidemiological analysis and disease control: MCDM is increasingly applied in health policy and decision-making to balance complex and diverse criteria, improving public health outcomes, patient care, and quality measurement. MCDM techniques like AHP and TOPSIS assist in evaluating multiple factors such as infection rates, geographic spread, population vulnerability, and healthcare capacity. For instance, during infectious disease outbreaks, MCDM allows health departments to optimise responses based on risk factors and intervention efficacy, aiding in the prioritisation of high-risk areas and resource allocation for vaccination, treatment, or quarantine measures (Hezer *et al.*, 2021).

Additionally, MCDM can model the effects of various interventions, helping policymakers decide on the best strategies for disease control by assessing potential outcomes based on factors like cost, reach, and expected reduction in infection rates (Hezer *et al.*, 2021). This approach is particularly valuable in pandemic preparedness, where balancing immediate response needs with long-term resource constraints is critical.

Application of MCDM in patient-centred care: MCDM's ability to weigh individual preferences and needs aligns well with patient-centred care models. By using methods such as fuzzy AHP and PROMETHEE, healthcare providers can tailor care plans based on patient-specific criteria like cultural preferences, treatment goals, side-effect tolerances, and quality of life. This approach supports shared decision-making by evaluating both clinical

and personal factors, empowering patients to have more control over their treatment choices (Ort *et al.*, 2023).

MCDM models help prioritise patient preferences in complex cases where multiple treatment options exist, ensuring that decisions are not solely driven by clinical efficacy but also by factors that matter most to patients. For example, in cancer treatment planning, MCDM can balance clinical outcomes with patient concerns about recovery times, side effects, and psychological impacts, making the care process more holistic and personalised (Frazão, 2018).

Generally, MCDM may have some limitations particularly in scenarios involving healthcare data where the precision and dynamic adaptability of the model are critical. MCDM techniques like AHP, TOPSIS rely heavily on fixed weighting systems and normalized scoring, which can limit their sensitivity to the distribution of data. These models often assume that decision criteria are equally distributed and comparable across options, which may not hold true in healthcare, where data can be highly skewed and heterogeneous. There is need for an improved MCDM that will assess criteria relative to their distribution within the dataset, giving a more practical understanding of each factor's performance relative to others. This allows for more interpretable results, especially in clinical contexts where small differences in rank can be significant.

While traditional MCDM methods focus on data-driven criteria alone, it does not incorporate clinical relevance weighting that will allow criteria to be adjusted not only based on statistical importance but also on clinical impact. This is especially critical in healthcare applications where certain features like blood pressure or cholesterol levels may be

clinically significant despite having lower statistical importance. There is need for an improvement that ensures that decisions align with both data insights and clinical priorities, improving both the validity and utility of the model in healthcare settings.

2.3.3 Data Mining in Health Monitoring

Data mining is the processing of raw data into useful information. This process sorts a large amount of data to identify the correlations, patterns and establish trends to solve a particular problem using a dedicated software tools and mathematical algorithms (Saeed and Memon, 2020). With the increase of health monitoring system outside the hospital environments using vital signs, research on mining and processing of vital sign measurements have grown tremendously. The objective of data mining in healthcare is to identify the correlations, patterns and establish trends in existing healthcare data. Research trends in health monitoring system centres basically on developing intelligent algorithms to perform a variety of the tasks. Data mining tasks can take two form: descriptive, and predictive (Siraj and Essgaer, 2011). Figure 2.2 presents data mining tasks and models.

Figure 2.2. Data mining tasks and models (Siraj and Essgaer, 2011).

The descriptive model usually results in recognizing the designs or relationships in data and discovers the properties of the data studied. This model often applies the unsupervised learning functions in identifying patterns describing the data that can be interpreted (Jothi *et al.*, 2015).

One of the easy and efficient descriptive tasks is clustering. Clustering function in modelling is to identify a finite set of categories or clusters to describe the data. It is an unsupervised data mining-based method that deals with the discovery of a structure in unlabeled data collection (Faizan *et al.*, 2020). Some algorithms are commonly used in clustering such as k-means, multivariate Gaussian mixture, hierarchical clustering, spectral and nearest neighbour methods (MayraZ, 2019). Clustering algorithm such as k-means is suitable in precision medicine. Precision medicine allows patients to be identified and treated by subgrouping patient data based on their molecular approach. For example Silitonga and Morina, (2018) used K-Means Clustering approach to find a trend pattern of patient illness based on disease code in Indonesia Case Base Groups (Ina CBG's).

Summarisation is another method in descriptive modelling used to analyse large dataset (Lesh and Mitzenmacher, 2004). Summarization is a concept in data mining that help to find a compact description by tabulating the mean and standard deviations in order to analyse data. Association rule in data mining is a technique used to observe frequently occurring patterns, correlations, or associations. Association rule has an impact when mining healthcare data. It helps to discover pattern and relationship between disease, status of patient health and symptoms (Kulkarni and Mundhe, 2017). One of the limitations of

association rule in healthcare mining is that it is not much needed in decision making system. The operation of Sequence analysis in data mining is to find a part in the data set that are alike and which parts differs. This is applicable in the field of healthcare such as analysis of gene expression, analysis of mutations in cancer, and protein structure prediction (Yu *et al.*, 2003).

Predictive modelling is a mining technique used to make inferences about uncertain future events (Dobbins *et al.*, 2017). However, predictive modelling can be applied to any unknown event regardless of when it occurred. A predictive model utilises a supervised learning approach as it involves feature extraction, training, and testing processes to predict data behaviour. (Banaee *et al.*, 2013). In healthcare context, predictive modelling is the “process that applies available data to identify persons who have high medical need and are ‘at risk’ for above-average future medical service utilization”(Vogenberg, 2009). Mostly predictive model is applied in disease prediction, diagnosis, and management.

Several researchers such as, Kwong, (2018) presented a prediction model of blood pressure for telemedicine, Parker *et al.* (2019) used prediction model to predict hospital admission at the emergency department triage. Some predictive modelling tasks include classification, prediction, regression, and time-series analysis. Classification task is a supervised technique where each instance belongs to a class (Sudhir *et al.*, 2017) classification model can be applied in the area of vital sign classification (Mena *et al.*, 2018), medical document classification (Dumnamene and Justice, 2018), and health traffic classification (Testi *et al.*, 2018). Regression is a predictive modelling technique used to predict a range of numeric

values in a particular dataset. Regression is applied in healthcare especially in the area of ranking disease risk factors (Cuadrado-Godia *et al.*, 2019) disease detection, prediction of mortality in critical illness. Time series analysis is a process of analyzing an observation of data points collected over a period of time. In the healthcare domain, time series is used to examine the transformation of behaviour over time.

2.3.4 Data mining process

The process of analysing data in health monitoring system entails extracting information from data generated from the sensor and linking it to the high knowledge representation. Research in health monitoring systems has focused more on data processing to identify and use more of the extracted information based on expert and user requirements. Data mining has been applied to all categories of health monitoring system. Generally, data mining process comprises five stages: data acquisition, data pre-processing, feature extraction/selection, modelling/learning stage, and visualization. The standard approach to data mining is presented in Figure 2.3.

Figure. 2.3. Data mining process (Banaee *et al.*, 2013)

2.3.5 Data acquisition

Data acquisition is the first stage when designing a health monitoring system. It utilises individualised or multiple sensory devices integrated in a wearable device to be placed under the biological tissue of a human. Data acquisition layer handles the acquisition of vital signs in real-time or continuous manner. Generally, the sensor used for data acquisition is based on the signals required. In CVD, most signals required for diagnosis and monitoring include pulse wave, electrocardiogram (ECG), phonocardiogram (PCG), photoplethysmography (PPG), seismocardiogram (SCG)/ ballistocardiographic (BCG), and blood pressure, (Lin *et al.*, 2021). Sensor like BMP180 (Singh, 2019), HEM-1000, OMRON (Ting-Wei and Shien-Fong, 2020) are used in post-stroke and patient self reported data for decision-making. Such data include; heartbeat data and sleeping rate (Adejumo, 2019). Others, especially in post-stroke rehabilitation include activity recognition, movement classification and clinical assessment emulation (Boukhenoufa *et al.*, 2022). A sensor named Holter (AthenaDiag, Medtronic) is used in measuring ECG (Carrarini *et al.*, 2022), ANNE™ One (Sibel Health;

Niles, IL, USA) was used in Chen *et al.* (2022) to collect data on self reported sleeping pattern from a post-stroke patient. Research conducted by Adejumo (2019) used Fitbit to collect heartbeat rate, sleeping rate, and the number of steps from a post-stroke patient.

Boukhenoufa *et al.* (2022) reveals that inertial measurement units sensor (IMUs) is a popular tool for collecting data from a post-stroke patient. Sensors such as the one developed by Abbott (Sylmar, CA, USA) were designed to directly measure pulmonary artery pressures. Additionally, the PPG sensor was used by Prakash (2019) to detect variations in blood flow in the finger. An optical-based heart rate monitoring sensor was developed to monitor the heart rate of patients (Fiber *et al.*, 2020). Table 2.7 presents a list of sensors used for data acquisition in cardiovascular patients.

Table2.7: Summary of selected sensors used for data acquisition in cardiovascular-related diseases

Papers	Sensor	Disease	Application
Esther <i>et al.</i> (2019)	Piezoelectric sensor	Coronary Heart Disease	To detect abnormal waveforms
Sumant <i>et al.</i> (2021)	CardioME MS	HF	To measures SBP, DBP and (PAP)
Prakash (2019)	PPG sensor	Heart Failure	To detects the variation of the blood flow in the finger
Carrarini <i>et al.</i> (2022)	Holter monitor	Stroke	Record electrical activities
Chen <i>et al.</i> (2022)	ANNE one	Post-stroke	measure triaxial acceleration as well as ECG, heart and respiratory rate, and proximal skin temperature
Adejumo (2019)	Fit bit	Post-stroke	Heartbeat rate
Singh (2019)	BMP180	Blood pressure	Measure temperature and pressure
Golbus <i>et al.</i> (2021)	HEM-1000, OMRON	Blood pressure	Heartbeat detection

2.3.6 Data pre-processing

Pre-processing of raw data in health monitoring system is vital to avoid the occurrence of noise, motion artefacts, and sensor errors. Pre-processing entails filter unusual data such as high frequency noise and artefacts (Shoka *et al.*, 2019). Data pre-processing is core to data mining process, especially in the preparation and transformation of data. The task of data pre-processing is to reduce data size, remove outliers, normalize data, find the relationship between data, and extract features from data (Wesam, 2017). Several authors have used different techniques for data pre-processing. For example Akhbarifar *et al.* (2020) used the feature selection methods to simplify data mining process in disease prediction. Chang *et al.* (2019) employed simple deletion, filling, and normalization of medical data for hypertension outcome prediction. Miller, (2020) suggest three approaches for pre-processing data: rescaling, making data binary [1 or 0] above or below a given threshold, and transforming variables.

Normalization is a data transformation process that improves the accuracy and efficiency of mining involving classification algorithms (Li *et al.*, 2017). In normalization, an attribute is normalized by reducing the size to a small specified range of 0.0 and 1.0 scaling its values so that they fall within a small-specified range, such as 0.0 to 1.0. There are different methods for data normalization. This include: min-max normalization (performing a linear transformation on the original data), z-score normalization (the values for and attribute A are normalized based on the mean and standard deviation of A), and normalization by decimal scaling by moving the decimal point of values of attribute A (Shalabi and Shaaban, 2006). Feature selection, is a pre-processing technique used in preparing high dimensional data.

This technique is vital in building a very simple and comprehensive model to improve mining performance, preparing clean and understandable data (Li *et al.*, 2017). Feature selection algorithm is categorized into supervised, unsupervised and semi-perspectives. However, the supervised perspective is usually designed for classification or regression problems to select a subset of features that are able to discriminate samples from different classes. Table 2.8 presents different techniques used in data pre-processing.

Table 2.8 Different techniques used in data pre-processing.

Papers	Techniques	Task	Disease
Khan and Algarni (2020)	median studentized residual approach	Replacing Missing Values, Normalization	Heart disease
Choi <i>et al.</i> (2021)	Z-score	Normalisation	Stroke
Nancy <i>et al.</i> (2022)	Kalman filtering	eliminates duplicate records, noise, and discrepancies in the data	Heart disease
Alazzam <i>et al.</i> (2021)	Feature Selection	To locate and eliminate duplicate data	Blood pressure
Miao, <i>et al.</i> (2020)	Noise filtering and Signal segmentation	to remove noise from original ECG signals, To reduce the signal variation and	Blood pressure
Ali, <i>et al.</i> (2020)	Kalman filtering	Filter and clean the data by removing noise, duplicate records, and inconsistencies	Heart disease

2.3.7 Feature extraction

Using a dataset with numerous features can cause a machine learning model to suffer from overfitting. Therefore, reducing the number of features in a dataset during data mining is very important. This can be accomplished by applying feature extraction techniques. The function of feature extraction is to create a new feature from the original dataset and then discard the original. Three common approaches to feature reduction are Principal Component Analysis (PCA), Independent Component Analysis (ICA), and Linear Discriminant Analysis (LDA) (Banaee et al., 2013). However, other techniques have also been applied for feature extraction. Pourhomayoun *et al.* (2020) used the univariate/multivariate method. Univariate in the context of feature extraction considers one feature at a time while multivariate considers subset of features together. This is important in computational and statistical scalability. Also, Chang *et al.* (2019) used the recursive feature elimination method. Liang *et al.* (2018) proposed a combination of filtering feature selection methods such as Spearman correlation, ReliefF, information gain (Info Gain), chi-square, mRMR, and the Gini index to mine medical data for hypertension assessment.

2.3.8 Modelling and learning methods

Several algorithms have been used for building models in health monitoring systems with medical data stored in a database. It is common to see models built for real-time processing using methods such as linear regression, nearest neighbors classifiers, decision trees, naïve Bayes classifiers, bayesian networks, support vector machines, neural networks, and ensemble methods. These models are built to make real-time diagnosis, prediction, classification, and monitoring activities. Of importance to note is the use of the K-star classification model for diagnosing hypertension (Akhbarifar *et al.*, 2020), Passing–Bablok

regression, and Bland–Altman analysis in accessing posture (Amitrano *et al.*, 2020). Table 2.9 presents different models and their applications.

Table 2.9: Selected algorithms and their applications in cardiovascular-related diseases

Ref	Algorithm	Disease	Application
Chae <i>et al.</i> (2020)	CNN	Chronic stroke survivors	Activity recognition
Egejuru <i>et al.</i> (2019)	ANFIS	Hypertension	Classification
Khan and Algarni, (2020)	ANFIS	Heart disease	Classification
Karaca <i>et al.</i> (2019)	ANN	Stroke	Diagnosis
Satoto <i>et al.</i> (2019)	Fuzzy Decision Tree	Hypertension	Estimate the discrete value of the target function
(Dumnamene and Justice, 2018)	Naïve Bayes	Heart disease	Document classification
(Nancy <i>et al.</i> , 2022)	Deep learning	Heart disease	Prediction
(Choi <i>et al.</i> , 2021)	Ensemble methods	Stroke	Prediction
Ali <i>et al.</i> (2020)	Deep learning	Heart disease	Prediction
Chatrati <i>et al.</i> (2020)	Ensemble method	Diabetes and hypertension	Prediction
Nashif <i>et al.</i> (2018)	Ensemble method	Heart disease	Prediction
Umer <i>et al.</i> (2022)	deep learning model	Heart failure	Detecting patient survival
Chen <i>et al.</i> (2022)	Ensemble method	Stroke	Classification of sleep stages
Miao <i>et al.</i> (2020)	Deep learning	Blood pressure	BP estimation

2.3.9 Visualisation

Visualisation is the final stage of the health monitoring lifecycle. The function of visualisation is to display the record of vital signs in real time. One unique feature of visualisation is the transformation of vital signs data and analysis into visual formats that helps users to understand patterns and detect abnormalities in large dataset. Also, visualization enables health professionals to understand the dataset and to make appropriate decisions about the patient. There are different applications used in visualisation. The application depends on the hosting application, the nature of the information projected, and its functionalities. For example, Miller (2020) proposed a smart healthcare monitoring system in IoT Environment to monitor heartbeat and body temperature. The paper used ThingSpeak for the graphical interpretation, and display of collected results. The result displayed by ThingSpeak shows the current status and process of transactions. Remote health monitoring of the elderly through wearable sensors was developed in Thar *et al.* (2019). The data was made available for the authorised people through a web application to access. LabVIEW was used in Raj *et al.* (2018) to help the medical practitioner evaluate data in a quantitative manner. Ali *et al.* (2020) identified Adafruit as a virtual platform that can be used as a communication medium between the user and the system through an application.

2.4 Related Works

2.4.1 Related works on remote monitoring system for hypertension

Desnanjaya and Nugraha (2024) presents an IoT-based BP monitoring device. The aim of the study was to facilitate the transmission of digital BP measurement and data to accessible application and website. The study adopts a comprehensive mixed-methods approach, which is commendable as it combines both qualitative and quantitative data to provide a well-rounded evaluation of the device. The hardware devices used for the study include MPX5050GP Pressure Sensor, Arduino Nano, NodeMCU ESP32. Linear regression technique was adopted to find the correlation between sensor readings and BP sensors. The choice of linear regression was to clearly identify the linear relationship between a dependent and independent variables in a dataset. However, linear regression takes out single output with weighted linear output. It does not consider interaction among the risk factors.

Egejuru *et al.* (2019) utilised a unified modelling language with extensible Mark-Up Language and Java programming language to develop a mobile-based hypertension risk monitoring system. JavaScript Object Notation was primarily used for data storage and retrieval mechanism of the system. The study adopted the 1999 WHO/ISH hypertension classification standard for the classification pattern. Adaptive neuro-fuzzy inference system (ANFIS) was used for the hypertension risk prediction. The simulation of the model was carried out using MATLAB ANFIS Toolbox. The system was an implementation of the internet in an offline tensimeter device using ESP8266. The result of the simulation shows 95% accuracy.

De Marchi *et al.* (2020) sought to improve Brazilian public health system by developing an electronic health platform for monitoring the health conditions of Patients. The study focused on the hypertensive patient. The system consists of a central server, dash board and a mobile application. The proposed electronic health platform was designed specifically for hypertension monitoring by incorporating risk assessment and counselling for healthy habit changes. The system is also capable of recording health conditions; receive notifications, reminders, and follow-up from health professionals. The system was built on the device equipped with modules of physiological sensors available in the market.

Gamification (game) method to improve user engagement for hypertension monitoring was presented in Cechetti *et al.* (2019). The system comprises two versions: application used to evaluate user engagement and acceptance of e-Lifestyle and the other with gamification. The non-gamified version displays the user's next reminders, profile, and last inserted measurements on the home screen for blood pressure, heartbeat, mood, sleeping, weight, waist circumference, body fat, and body mass index. The gamified version displays a progress bar with the level completion percentage and the number of points the user has earned. Users have access to specific recommendations according to their health profile. The user can also check the number of points he or she can get by complying with recommendations. A questionnaire was used to evaluate the Acceptance, Engagement, and Analysis of usage logs. The result from the evaluation indicates that applying gamification to a system can eventually boost engagement, provide key factors such as involvement, curiosity, and enjoyment to users. However, one of the challenges to be noted in this study

is balancing entertainment with clinical effectiveness. Preclusion should be taken to ensure that the gamification elements do not distract from the primary health monitoring objectives.

2.4.2 Related works on risk stratification models

Cox *et al.*(2022) developed a machine learning models that will enable risk stratification of 30-day procedure-related mortality and 30-day unplanned read- mission in patients undergoing lower extremity infra-inguinal endovascular interventions. 14,444 cases obtained from the American College of Surgeons National Surgical Quality Improvement Program database were used for the analysis. Different machine learning algorithm such as Support Vector Machines (SVM), Multilayer Perceptrons (MLP), Gradient Boosting Machines (GBM), and Random Forest (RF) were used for the study. Most of the machine learning algorithms used in the study demonstrated their effectiveness in risk stratification. However issues related to model interpretability need to be addressed since most of the machine learning algorithms used in the study are regarded as black box.

Rim *et al.* (2021) developed a cardiovascular risk stratification model using coronary artery calcium scores predicted from retinal photographs. A total of 216 152 retinal photographs from five datasets (South Korea, Singapore, and the UK) were used to train and validate the algorithms. Deep learning algorithm was used for the model and area under the receiver operating characteristic curve (AUC) was used in measuring the performance of the model. Deep-learning models used in this study are often considered "black-box" models, this implies that their decision-making process is not easily interpretable. Clinicians may be reluctant to use models whose predictions cannot be fully explained.

Rosenkranz *et al.* (2022) developed a scoring tool to identify COVID-19 patients at risk for severe illness during the Omicron wave. Logistic regression was used to train data from a large cohort study within Israel's second-largest healthcare maintenance organisation. Different predictors such as age, immunosuppression, pregnancy, vaccination status, and prior COVID-19 infection was also used. The model is a scoring tool to assess COVID-19 severity during the Omicron wave aiding health professionals to prioritise resources for high-risk patients. The simple nature of logistic regression was advantageous to the study. However, this model did not assume linear relationships between predictors and outcomes, which may not fully capture the complex interactions of COVID-19 risk factors.

Ruiz-Ramos *et al.* (2024) used a retrospective cohort study, from multiple hospitals in Catalonia, Spain to develop a predictive model for emergency department (ED) revisits, hospital admissions, and mortality based on patient characteristics and pharmacotherapy. The study used logistic regression with a "stepwise-forward" approach based on the Bayesian Information Criterion (BIC). The model incorporated 44 medication groups, assessed using Anatomical Therapeutic Chemical (ATC) codes, to account for drug-related problems (DRPs). The model is helpful especially for aging population whose ability to understand the risks associated with multiple medications are crucial. Also the study used real-world data to ensure that the model is grounded in the complexities and variability of actual patient care. This will influence the outcome of the model when implemented in similar settings.

Zhao *et al.* (2022) used multivariate logistic analysis on data obtained from 10,164 individuals across 175 centres in China to develop and validate a faecal immunochemical test (FIT)-based risk-stratification model for colorectal neoplasia (CN) in China. The study aim was to create the National Colorectal Polyp Care (NCPC) score. The model was designed to stratify individuals into low, intermediate, and high-risk categories. Result from the study demonstrates high accuracy in identifying CN, advanced CN (ACN), and colorectal cancer (CRC). The high performance of the model proves its ability to improve early detection and resource allocation in colorectal cancer screening. Many influential risk factors were incorporated. It may not represent all potential variables influencing colorectal neoplasia. Risk factors like relevant clinical or lifestyle factors were not captured thereby affecting the accuracy of the model.

Shi *et al.* (2023) developed a risk stratification model for cervical squamous cell carcinoma (CSCC). The study employed recursive partitioning analysis (RPA) and Cox regression analysis on a retrospective cohort of 664 women treated with definitive radiotherapy. International Federation of Gynecology and Obstetrics (FIGO) staging was combined with squamous cell carcinoma antigen (SCC-Ag) levels. The model divides the patients into three categories (high, intermediate, and low-risk groups). Post-treatment SCC-Ag and FIGO stage are the target variables for overall survival. The performance evaluation of the model showed its ability to guide treatment decisions and improve prognostic accuracy in CSCC. One limitation of the study is that it is a single centre study: data was collected from a single institution, which limits the generalisability of the model to other

populations or healthcare settings. Validation in multiple centres or in different geographic locations would be necessary to confirm the model's broader applicability.

Rim *et al.* (2021) proposed a deep-learning algorithm (RetiCAC) to predict coronary artery calcium (CAC) presence in retinal photographs. The stratified RetiCAC score, was used to predict cardiovascular events. Pooled Cohort Equation (PCE) was integrated into RetiCAC score to enhance cardiovascular risk prediction, demonstrating the potential of deep learning in non-invasive risk assessment. One limitation of the study was its reliance which may not provide sufficient quality in all clinical settings. Additionally, Deep-learning models are often considered "black-box" models, implying that their decision-making process is not easily interpretable especially to clinician and other user of the model. This will pose a serious challenge on its usage in the clinical setting.

Hou *et al.* (2021) developed a prognostic model to predict disease-free survival (DFS) in early-stage breast cancer (BC) patients treated with neoadjuvant chemotherapy (NAC). Nomogram algorithm was used to categorise patients into different group (low, moderate, and high-risk) using the total points derived from independent prognostic variables such as clinical stage, receptor status, and cancer burden. The performance evaluation of the model especially its ability to stratify patients accurately into risk categories demonstrates its usefulness in personalising treatment plans and improving patient outcomes in breast cancer. The study is a single centre study which involves the use of single hospital to collect data for the validation. This may limit its generalisability to other clinical settings with different patient populations or treatment protocols.

Kumar *et al.* (2022) developed a risk stratification score that will identify patient likelihood of developing slow-flow/no-reflow (SF/NR) during primary percutaneous coronary intervention (PCI) in STEMI patients. Nine risk factor presumed to have impact on SF/NR was used for the risk stratification model. Dataset of 1,711 patients undergoing primary PCI was used. Candidate variable was shortlisted from twenty seven (27) selected characterises using Univariate logistic analysis. Performance metrics such as sensitivity and specificity were used to determine the performance of the risk stratification model. Results show a sensitivity of 77.9% and specificity of 62.6%. The main drawback of the study is that it was conducted in a single centre. This may restrict the applicability of the findings to other institutions with diverse patient's population. or procedural practices. Also the use of Univariate logistic analysis may hinder the usability of the risk stratification model by clinician as most regression model lack transparency in the computational process.

Wang *et al.* (2023) conducted a retrospective study to provide prognosis in acute ischemic stroke (AIS) patient using Random Forest. Data was obtained from electronic health record from Xuzhou Medical University hospital. Six hundred and seventy seven (677) instances were used for the study. Prognosis variable such as NSE, HCY, and CRP were used to stratify patients. The result of the analysis showed high accuracy (AUC 0.908). Incorporation of feature importance to select influential risk factor gave strengthen the interpretability of the model. However, the study is a single centre study. This may limit the applicability of the findings to other populations or clinical settings. Random Forest model

used in this study is a "black-box" model, hence interpretability of the output results by clinicians is not possible.

2.4.3 Related literature on hypertension risk Stratification model

Kanwar *et al.* (2020) studied the effectiveness of Bayesian network-based machine learning in enhancing the predictive ability of an existing state-of-the-art risk stratification tool, REVEAL 2.0. The study proposed an advanced risk stratification model based on Bayesian network-based machine learning pulmonary arterial hypertension. Data was obtained from the REVEAL registry to derive the PHORA model using the same variables and cut-points used in REVEAL 2.0. The 2015 European Society of Cardiology/European Respiratory Society guidelines were used to stratify patients into risk categories (low-risk, intermediate-risk, and high-risk) based on their 12-month mortality predictions. Result from the performance evaluation demonstrated that the PHORA model outperformed REVEAL 2.0 in predicting 1-year survival, as evidenced by an area under the curve (AUC) of 0.80 compared to 0.76 for REVEAL 2.0.

While the PHORA model represents advancement in the stratification of PAH risk, several limitations must be acknowledged, particularly when considering risk stratification as a multi-criteria decision-making (MCDM) problem. Although Bayesian networks are designed to model the interrelationships between variables, the assumption of conditional independence between parent and child nodes can be limiting. In complex clinical scenarios where multiple variables interact in a nonlinear and interdependent manner, this assumption may oversimplify the relationships, potentially leading to less accurate predictions. The

study approached risk stratification as primarily a classification problem rather than a multi-criteria decision-making problem. In MCDM context, the challenge is to balance and integrate multiple criteria that may conflict with one another. For instance, improving survival predictions might require different prioritisation of variables compared to predicting quality of life or long-term complications. The PHORA model, even though advanced, may not fully capture the trade-offs between these different clinical outcomes because it focuses on optimising a single criterion (1-year survival). Although the PHORA model improved discrimination over REVEAL 2.0, the AUC scores, especially in external validations (0.74 in COMPERA), suggest there is still room for improvement in distinguishing between risk levels. In stratification tasks that involve multiple criteria, a higher degree of separation between groups is often required to ensure that interventions are appropriately targeted. The moderate improvement in AUC might not be sufficient in clinical settings where precise stratification is crucial. The study highlights PHORA's ability to tolerate missing data elements, which is strength of Bayesian networks.

Boutilier *et al.* (2021) developed a risk stratification algorithm for diabetes and hypertensive patient using machine learning algorithm. This study was intended to improve the accuracy of detecting high-risk individuals within the populations of urban slums of Hyderabad, India during community-based screening programs. The study used electronic medical data of 2278 patients. The data collection process was between July 14, 2015, and April 21, 2018. The data was used to train and test various machine learning models. Random forest model demonstrated superiority in prediction accuracy for both diabetes and hypertension. The performance of the models was compared with the other existing model most especially

those developed in the United States and the United Kingdom. Random forest model outperformed those models. One of the limitations of the study is the stratification process adopted. The study used clinical and demographic risk factors, such as age, blood pressure, and blood glucose levels but failed to address other important risk factor such as lifestyle, environmental influences, and genetic predispositions. Failure to include these risk factors limits the scope of the model.

Forte *et al.* (2021) developed a decision rule model for diabetes and hypertension by stratifying coronary artery disease. The major objective of the study is to improve on previously used clinical risk scores by integrating genetic data, which is often ignored in traditional models. Dataset for the study was obtained using a large cohort of 60,782 UK Biobank participants. The performance of the model was assessed using the AUROC and Net Reclassification Index (NRI). The strength of the study is the incorporation of genetic risk scores alongside traditional biomarkers and physical measurements. This proved that genetic factors play a critical role in the risk of cardiometabolic conditions. The uses of a large cohort from the UK Biobank improved the generalisability of the model. The size of the dataset also enhanced the model by enabling robust statistical analysis and the development of more reliable predictive models. A comparative analysis of the algorithm was conducted against existing clinical risk scores. The results provide valuable insights into the potential of integrating genetic risk to enhance risk stratification and prediction.

One of the limitations of this study is the introduction of genetic risk scores for stratification process as a linear combination of factors rather than addressing it as a complex multi-

criteria decision-making (MCDM) problem. This limitation hinders the interactions between different risk factors. If hypertension risks stratification must be addressed as a multi-criteria decision problem then, factors such as age, lifestyle, genetic predispositions, and environmental influences will have non-linear relationship which the study failed to fully capture.

Cheng *et al.* (2022) conducted a study to ascertain if cardiovascular risk is more tightly related with central (cSBP) than brachial (bSBP) systolic pressure using a meta-analysis of International Database of Central Arterial Properties. The study emphasised the possibility of using different risk to improve the accuracy of cardiovascular risk prediction. The use of cloud-based storage for large datasets ensures scalability and straight of the model performance. However, the study underscored the need for comprehensive risk assessment tools that consider multiple health indicators beyond just blood pressure.

A model to predict the ten year risk of premature cardiovascular disease (CVD) and mortality among women with hypertensive disorders of pregnancy (HDP) was developed in Ukah *et al.* (2020). The study used Cox proportional hazards regression to create a prediction model. Performance evaluation of the model was assessed using (AUC) and the result revealed an AUC of 0.66. The result indicates that the model can differentiate between those who will and will not experience premature CVD. However the authors acknowledged the need for additional clinical variables and external validation before clinical application considering the fact that the discriminative ability of the model is somewhat low. The model's can be viewed as a multi-criteria decision problem for it primary aim of classifying individuals into risk categories. The criteria involved are many such as age, history of HDP,

and other clinical variables which makes it complex. The relatively low performance of the model indicates that the model may not effectively integrate these criteria into the risk assessment model.

2.4.4 Summary of literature review

Findings from Kanwar *et al.* (2020) and Cheng *et al.* (2022) show the need to develop a model with high prediction accuracy. However, such model as reflected in their studies suffers from limited interpretability. This will pose critical challenges in clinical settings where transparency and a clear understanding of decision-making processes are crucial. The issue of balancing the trade-off between machine learning models complexity and their interpretability remains paramount, suggesting the need for further research into models that can maintain both high predictive power and transparency.

Studies in Boutilier *et al.* (2021) and Forte *et al.* (2021) emphasise the need to integrate various types of data such as clinical records, patient-reported outcomes, and genetic factors into risk stratification model to boost the comprehensiveness of hypertension risk stratification. However, the combination of multiple data can introduce complexity that hinders practical implementation most especially self-reported data, ensuring the generalisability of certain genetic markers. Therefore, there is need for simplification strategies to effectively manage these biases for real-world applications.

Balancing simplicity with accuracy is also a major challenge in the model developed by Kanwar *et al.* (2020) who proposed a simple, user-friendly tool to be used by broad range of

healthcare providers. Simplifying models to improve usability is important; but simplifying models often requires excluding risk factors. This will no doubt reduce prediction accuracy of the model. This represents an ongoing challenge of creating models that appropriately balance simplicity with comprehensiveness, especially in light of emerging risk factors such as socioeconomic status and social determinants of health.

Cheng *et al.* (2022) proposed innovative approaches to hypertension prediction using temporal patterns and deep learning techniques. Despite the history of prediction accuracy of the model, the practical application of such models is limited by their complexity and the "black box" nature of deep learning algorithms. Thus, there is need of development of user-friendly, resource-efficient models that are transparent and explainable.

Ukah *et al.* (2020), highlighted the importance of tailoring risk stratification models to underserved groups. However, the moderate low discriminatory power and lack of external validation in their model suggest the need for more robust approaches that can account for the multi-dimensional nature of hypertension risk while being applicable across diverse populations.

The complexity of hypertension risk involving multiple factors such as genetics, lifestyle, and socioeconomic status, suggest the need for models that incorporate multi-criteria decision-making (MCDM). Such approaches can better capture multi-dimensional nature of hypertension risk, providing a more comprehensive assessment that can inform personalised treatment strategies.

The reviewed paper collectively contributed to the field of hypertension risk stratification but also have some area of limitations where further research is needed. Key areas include improving model interpretability, integrating diverse data sources while managing complexity, balancing simplicity with accuracy, and ensuring external validation. Additionally, the application of multi-criteria decision models could offer a more holistic approach to hypertension risk assessment, addressing the complex interplay of factors involved. These findings underscore the importance of continued innovation and validation to develop models that are both clinically relevant and practically applicable. By leveraging Percentile Rank Based Multi-criteria Decision Making algorithm, this research fills the gap by providing a decision rule-based stratification model that enhances interpretability while maintaining high accuracy.

CHAPTER THREE

3.0

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 Design of the Research Process

This study sets four specific objectives to be carried out in achieving the aim of developing a Remote hypertension Monitoring and Risk Stratification Model. The research design adopted consists of eight (8) phases shown in Figure 3.1.

Figure 3.1: The framework of the developed research process design

From Figure 3.1, the research process design adopted is subdivided into four (4) main steps. First, is the identification and prioritisation of hypertension key risk factors to be used for

the development of remote hypertension monitoring and risk stratification model. The second step involved the formulation of a PRBMCDM algorithm. The third step is the development and implementation of the formulated PRBMCDM algorithm. The fourth step is the performance evaluation of the monitoring and risk stratification model. Figure 3.2 present the proposed remote hypertension monitoring and risk stratification model.

Figure.3.2: Proposed remote hypertension monitoring and risk stratification model

3.1.1 Data acquisition layer

The Data acquisition Layer is responsible for the remote collection of physiological data from patients. This layer comprises various medical-grade sensors and wearable devices that monitor blood pressure levels. Priorities are given to the type of sensors used to ensure

accuracy, battery life, and patients comfort. The data acquisition process is governed by standard medical procedure of collecting hypertension data ensuring that the data are collected at regular intervals, free of distortion from noise.

3.1.2 Data transmission layer

Data transmission layer capture the data transmission through the central server or cloud infrastructure. The design of this layer introduced redundancy and failover mechanisms to prevent data loss in the event of network interruptions. The layer supports various connectivity options such as Wi-Fi and 4G/5G to accommodate different environments where patients may be residing.

3.1.3 Data processing and analysis layer

The engine of the monitoring model is in the Data Processing and Analysis Layer. This layer hosts the PRBMCDM for the remote hypertension monitoring. The raw data obtained from data collection layer is sent to this layer first for pre-processing. Pre-processing task involves data normalisation, filtering, and the handling of missing data. The processed data is then fed into the PRBMCDM model for analysis. The second task of this layer is to enable the PRBMCDM to stratify patients into different risk categories based on the derived metrics, considering both the data-driven insights and clinical significance. The third task is to use the risk stratification output to provide actionable recommendations to healthcare professionals.

3.1.4 User interface layer

The User Interface Layer visualises the analysis results to healthcare providers and patients. This layer is designed to be user-centric, offering intuitive dashboards and real-time alerts.

For healthcare providers, it provides detailed reports on patient status, trends over time, and risk stratification outcomes. For patients, it delivers personalised feedback and recommendations, empowering them to take proactive steps in managing their hypertension. The architecture is flexible enough to support various interface devices, including smartphones, tablets, and desktop computers.

3.2 Identification and Prioritisation of Hypertension Key Risk Factors

The first objective of this thesis is to identify and prioritise hypertension key risk factors for remote hypertension monitoring and risk stratification model. This objective will be achieved through a comprehensive methodological procedure that includes obtaining ethical clearance from relevant authority, organise a focus group discussion, collection of data, data pre-processing and feature importance determination and selection. This will pave way for the formulation and implementation of remote hypertension monitoring and risk stratification model. Figure 3.3 presents the methodological procedure for objective one (1).

Figure 3.3: Methodological procedures for objective one

3.2.1 Ethical consideration

For this study, the authors formally applied to the Kogi State Ministry of Health Lokoja, Nigeria for permission to carry out a study. The application was approved by the Health Research Ethics Committee of the ministry following the invitation of the applicant and clarification regarding the study and its objectives. An ethical clearance certificate was issued. Copy of the request letter and the ethical clearance certificate are presented in appendices A and B.

3.2.2 Identification of risk factors

It is common practice to obtain variables that will be used for hypertension risk stratification model are obtained from analysis of relevant clinical literature combined with

the opinions of health professionals who are well-versed in the signs, symptoms and associated risk factors (Martínez, 2017). In this study, focus group session was organised to bring together health professionals to brainstorm on variables to be used as risk factors in the study.

To identify variables to be included in the model, four sessions of the focus group were organised. Six health professionals from the healthcare sector (medical doctors and registered nurses) with strong experience dealing with hypertension cases and working in different communities across the area under study were selected to participate in the focus group session.

The aim of organising focus group session is to bring in health professionals to brainstorm and arrive at a list of risk factors to be included in the stratification model of hypertensive patients among the study population. Four sessions were organised. Each of the sessions lasted an average of forty five (45) minutes and took place in Amnesty Hospital, off Governors Lodge Street Ankpa, Kogi State. Each session was coordinated by the researcher with previous knowledge from literature review of hypertension stratification models. Notes were taken by the researcher on the discussions.

Nominal Group technique (NGT) was used in each of the sessions to arrive at a definite conclusion on key issues for the scheduled discussion. The goals to be achieved in each of the sessions were itemised by the researcher. Observations, summaries and reflections

derived from the discussions were used to design hypertension risk factors. Table 3.1 presents the protocol that was followed in the focus group session.

Table 3.1: Protocol followed for the focus group session

Session	Task	Objective
1	Introduction of the project, researcher and the medical professionals.	To introduce the research aim and objectives and the recognition of each participant of the focus group.
2	Study 15 hypertension clinical cases put together by the health professionals with a profile characterised by: a) age b) Gender c) Location d) occupation e)Diabetes f) with and without family history of hypertension g)cholesterol level h)blood pressure reading h) hypertension risk level.	To draw enabling and potential variables that may determine hypertension risk levels.
3	Discuss the prevalence of each risk factor on hypertension, deliberate on the importance of each risk factor in hypertension diagnosis and risk stratification.	To deliberate and select the most prevalent hypertension risk factors.
4	Discussion on the definition of each risk factor, measurement and method of extracting the information from hospital case files.	To operationalise the selected risk factors. To detect the information sources for data collection.

The output derived from these meetings is a list of hypertension risk factors to be tested for the development of the risk stratification model. Table 3.2 presents the risk factors.

Table 3.2: Hypertension risk factors

S/NO	Attribute Name	Attribute Description	Label Name
1	Age	The person's age(year)	40-49 , 50 – 59 , 60 – 69 ≥70
2	Gender	The person gender	Male, Female
3	FHH	Family history of Hypertension	Yes, No
4	DBM	Diabetes Mellitus	Yes, No
5	SS	Smoking Status	Smoker, Non smoker
6	TCH	Total cholesterol	<149mg/dl, 150-199mg/dl, 200-249mg/dl
7	OCCP	Occupation	Civil Servant= Business=2, Farmer =3
8	LOC	Location	Urban=1,Rural=2
9	HG	Hypertension Grade	Grade 1, Grade 2, Grade 3
10	HRL	Hypertension risk Level	High risk, Medium risk, Low risk

3.2.3 Data collection

Data collection for this study was carried out from March 2022 to February 2023 in some selected public and private hospitals in Kogi Eastern Senatorial District, Nigeria. Information was extracted from the hospital case files of the patients undergoing hypertension treatment in the outpatient Department. The patients consist of both genders (male and female) of adult age. Any Patient who does not have the necessary information for risk stratification in the hospital case files was not considered and therefore excluded from the data collected. Data were collected from 15 private and public hospitals. The list of hospitals used for the exercise is presented in table 3.3. Some management of the hospitals

offered short training on the method of extracting the information from the hospital case file. The risk factors include socio-demographic variables, socio-economic variables, clinical variables, clinical history and types of hypertension. In the data collection, patient names were not recorded. The collection of the data was guided by the instructions and directives of the outpatient nurses. 1793 instances collected from the hospital case files were saved in excel format. The sample of the dataset is presented in Figure 3.4.

Table 3.3: List of Hospital Used for Data Collection

S/No	Name of Hospital	LGA	No of Records
1	General Hospital Ankpa	Ankpa	256
2	Amnesty Hospital Ankpa	Ankpa	114
3	KSCOE staff clinic	Ankpa	78
4	General Hospital Dekina	Dekina	151
5	General Hospital Egume	Dekina	62
6	S&A Hospital Anyigba	Dekina	103
7	General Hospital Ugwolawo	Ofu	80
8	Onuche Memorial Clinic Ugwolawo	Ofu	74
9	General Hospital Idah	Idah	192
10	Nativity Hospital Idah	Idah	52
11	General hospital Odolu	Igalamela	137
12	General Hospital Oguma	Bassa	120
13	Gboloko cottage Hospital	Bassa	116
14	General Hospital Okpo	Olamaboro	171
15	Ogugu Cottage Hospital	Olamaboro	87
	Total		1793

AGE	Gender	Loc Gov	Locc	Occp	FHH	DBM	S.S	TCH	SBP	DBP	HI
57	MALE	Ankpa	Urban	Civil servant	YES	NO	Non-smoker	150-200mg/dl	140mmHg	90mmHg	Medium
63	MALE	Ankpa	Urban	Civil servant	YES	NO	Non-smoker	150-200mg/dl	153mmHg	92mmHg	Medium
54	FEMALE	Ankpa	Rural	Civil servant	YES	YES	Non-smoker	200-250 mg/dL	164mmHg	98mmHg	High Ri
58	MALE	Ankpa	Urban	Business	NO	NO	Non-smoker	150-200 mg/dL	140mmHg	82mmHg	Low Ri
61	MALE	Ankpa	Urban	Business	YES	NO	Smoker	250-300 mg/dL	156mmHg	95mmHg	High Ri
60	FEMALE	Ankpa	Urban	Civil servant	YES	NO	Non-smoker	200-250 mg/dL	145mmHg	92mmHg	Low Ri
59	MALE	Ankpa	Urban	Civil servant	NO	NO	Smoker	200-250 mg/dL	159mmHg	97mmHg	Medium
64	MALE	Ankpa	Urban	Civil servant	YES	NO	Non-smoker	150-200mg/dl	153mmHg	94mmHg	Medium
60	MALE	Ankpa	Rural	Farmer	NO	YES	Non-smoker	250-300 mg/dL	164mmHg	96mmhg	Medium
68	MALE	Ankpa	Urban	Business	YES	YES	Smoker	200-250 mg/dL	152mmHg	96mmhg	High Ri
55	MALE	Ankpa	Urban	Business	YES	NO	Non-smoker	200-250 mg/dL	156mmHG	94mmHg	Medium
67	FEMALE	Ankpa	Urban	Business	YES	YES	Non-smoker	250-300 mg/dL	153mmHg	94mmHg	High Ri
56	MALE	Ankpa	Urban	Business	NO	NO	Non-smoker	200-250mg/dl	142mmHg	91mmHg	Low Ri
57	MALE	Ankpa	Urban	Business	YES	NO	Non-smoker	150-200 mg/dL	156mmHg	95mmHg	Medium
65	MALE	Ankpa	Rural	Farmer	YES	NO	Non-smoker	<150 mg/dL	178mmHg	90mmHg	Medium
59	FEMALE	Ankpa	Rural	Business	YES	YES	Non-smoker	150-200 mg/dL	162mmHg	96mmhg	Medium
49	MALE	Ankpa	Urban	Business	YES	NO	Non-smoker	200-250 mg/dL	153mmHg	90mmHg	Medium
65	MALE	Ankpa	Rural	Civil servant	YES	NO	Non-smoker	<150mg/dl	168mmHg	94mmHg	Medium
67	FEMALE	Ankpa	Urban	Business	YES	YES	Non-smoker	200-250 mg/dL	149mmHg	98mmHg	High Ri
54	MALE	Ankpa	Urban	Business	NO	NO	Smoker	150-200 mg/dL	141mmHg	94mmHg	Low Ri
55	MALE	Ankpa	Urban	Business	YES	NO	Smoker	200-250 mg/dL	153mmHg	97mmHg	High Ri
66	FEMALE	Ankpa	Urban	Civil servant	YES	NO	Non-smoker	200-250 mg/dL	147mmHg	90mmHg	High Ri
62	MALE	Ankpa	Urban	Civil servant	NO	NO	Non-smoker	150-200mg/dl	143mmHg	90mmHg	Low Ri

Figure 3.4: Dataset sample in excel format

3.2.4 Data pre-processing

To prepare the hypertension dataset for analysis, the following pre-processing steps in Figure 3.5 were implemented.

Figure 3.5: Stages of data pre-processing

3.2.4.1 Data cleaning

Removing duplicates: Duplicate records, identified through patient IDs and key attributes, were removed to avoid redundancy and ensure each patient was represented once, preventing skewed analysis results.

3.2.4.2 Statistical analysis

This section presents the statistical methods applied to the dataset to explore, summarise, and interpret key characteristics relevant to hypertension risk. The aim is to extract meaningful patterns, trends, and associations within the data, providing foundational insights for the risk stratification model. In this study, descriptive statistics were calculated to summarise the distribution of variables such as age, total cholesterol, systolic and diastolic blood pressure, and other socio-demographic and clinical factors. Measures such as frequency distributions were used to provide an overview of the sample characteristics and guide initial data interpretation.

3.2.4.3 Feature importance determination and selection

In model development, some risk factors that are perceived to be influential to a target class may turn out to be non-informative and redundant or vice versa. Variable selection using statistical tools could potentially reveal the importance of each risk factor. Feature importance and selection reduces the computational complexity of prediction algorithms especially when non-informative or redundant input features from the dataset are removed. This action will increase the prediction accuracy and overall performance of the model. In this study, Drop column importance, also known as leave-one-out feature importance is used. It is a technique used to measure the importance of each feature in a predictive model. Unlike permutation feature importance, which shuffles the values of a feature, drop column importance involves completely removing the feature from the dataset and then retraining the model to evaluate the change in performance.

For the feature selection process, any feature that, when removed, results in a decrease of less than one (1) in the model's performance will be considered insignificant and will be dropped. This threshold ensures that only features with significant impact on the model's predictive capability is retained, simplifying the model and potentially improving its generalisation on data. Algorithm for determining feature importance is presented in Table 3.4.

Table 3.4: Algorithm for feature importance determination

*Input: Tabular dataset S where $S \in (N, P)$ with N instances and P features
Fit a classification model $f(x)$ using all P features on the dataset S*

Output: Features with higher value

1. *Begin*
2. *Calculate the accuracy A of $f(x)$ in S using all P features on the dataset S .*
3. *For each feature (p_i) in P :*
 - a. *Remove p_i from the dataset S , resulting in reduced dataset $S - \{p_i\}$*
 - b. *Fit the classification model $f(x)$ to $S - \{p_i\}$*
 - c. *Calculate the accuracy $A - \{p_i\}$ of the model on $S - \{p_i\}$*
 - d. *Calculate the importance score x_i for feature p_i the drop in accuracy:
$$x_i = A - (A - \{p_i\})$$*
4. *Repeat step (3) for all features p_i in P until all features have been evaluated*
5. *Sort the feature importance score x_1 in descending order to get the feature ranking.*
$$x_{\text{sort}} = x_1 > x_2 > x_3 > \dots > x_p$$
6. *To select the feature subset*
 - a. *Select the predetermined number of top features based on the ranking.*
 - b. *Exclude features that have low importance measure values.*
 - c. *Select the features that have higher importance values compared to the rest.*
7. *End*

3.3 Formulation of Hypertension Risk Stratification Model Using PRBMCDM

Algorithm

The second objective of this study is the formulation of hypertension risk stratification model using PRBMCDM algorithm. This concept helps in allocating risk to individual instances based on multi-criteria's that captures the main aspects and scope of hypertension risk management. This model assigns rating to each risk factor (age, gender, family history of hypertension, diabetes mellitus, smoking, and cholesterol) ranging from zero (0) to one (1), where one (1) implies that the risk for the given instance is true and zero (0) implies false such that the sum of the risk factors and the hypertension grade determines the risk

weight of the individual instances. The calculated risk weight calculated will be compared with the threshold to stratify the risk level.

3.3.1 Hypertension grade

The Hypertension Grade (HG) is based on the International Society of Hypertension (ISH) guidelines; it is a classification mechanism that assigns a score based on systolic blood pressure (SBP) and diastolic blood pressure (DBP) levels. This is presented in equation 3.1.

$$HG = g(SBP, DBP) = \begin{cases} g_1 \text{ if } (140 \leq SBP < 160 \text{ or } 90 \leq DBP < 100) \\ g_2 \text{ if } (160 \leq SBP < 180 \text{ or } 100 \leq DBP < 110) \\ g_3 \text{ if } (SBP \geq 180 \text{ or } DBP \geq 110) \end{cases} \quad (3.1)$$

Where,

HG = hypertension grade,

g = grade,

SBP = systolic blood pressure,

DBP = diastolic blood pressure.

3.3.2 Gender -specific age classification

The gender-specific age classification assigns risk points based on age and gender, recognising that hypertension risk increases at different ages for men and women. Women aged 65 and above and men aged 55 and above are considered higher-risk groups. The gender-specific age classification is presented in equation 3.2.

$$A = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if Gender} = 0 \text{ and Age} \geq 65 \\ 1 & \text{if Gender} = 1 \text{ and Age} \geq 55 \end{cases} \quad (3.2)$$

Where,

A= gender- specific age classification

I= indicator

Gender = 0 represents female and

Gender = 1 represents male.

3.3.3 PRBMCDM mathematical framework

In the proposed PRBMCDM mathematical framework, the hypertension training dataset s_i is a set of classified records, S_1, S_2, \dots, S_n , where each record represents an individual with his/her associated risk factors. These risk factors, denoted as $rf = \{a_1 = AGE, a_2 = gender, a_3 = FHH, a_4 = DBM, a_5 = SS, a_6 = TCH\}$, are used to assess the hypertension risk. The total risk factor is defined as a function that sums all the individual risk factors, represented as α , such that:

$$\begin{aligned} \alpha_i &= g_i + a_1 + a_2 + \dots + a_n \\ &= g_i + \sum_{i=1}^n a_i \end{aligned} \quad (3.3)$$

Where,

α_i = the sum of all the risk factors

a_i = specific risk weight of individual instance in the dataset with Index, i .

g_i = specific grade point of individual instances in the dataset with index i

The risk weights are sorted in an ascending order such that

$$\alpha_{sort} = \alpha_1 < \alpha_2 < \alpha_3 < \dots < \alpha_n \quad (3.4)$$

The hypertension risk threshold is determined by analysing the percentile ranks of the individual risk factors. The dataset is divided into three subsets, each subset representing a risk level: High Risk (3), Medium Risk (2), and Low Risk (1). To define these thresholds, the 33rd percentile and 67th percentile of the dataset are used. Low risk corresponds to values falling between the 1st and 33rd percentile, Medium risk corresponds to values between the 34th and 67th percentile, and High risk corresponds to values between the 68th and 100th percentile. These percentile boundaries are denoted as β_1 (33rd percentile) and β_2 (67th percentile), which help in stratifying the hypertension risk levels based on the distribution of the risk factors in the dataset.

$$\beta_1 = \frac{p_1}{100} [N + 1] \quad (3.5)$$

$$\beta_2 = \frac{p_2}{100} [N + 1] \quad (3.6)$$

Where,

β_1 = the lower limit of the risk weight

β_2 = the upper limit of the risk weight

p_1 = (33%)

p_2 = (67%)

N = the total number of instances in the dataset

If either β_1 or β_2 is not an integer, the midpoint between the floor and ceiling values of β_1 and β_2 , respectively, is calculated to establish an accurate threshold.

Where,

The floor of β_1 = the greatest integer less than or equal to β_1

The ceiling of β_2 = the smallest integer greater than or equal to β_2

$$\beta_1 = \frac{p_1}{100} [N + 1] \longrightarrow \frac{\text{floor}(\beta_1) + \text{ceil}(\beta_1)}{2} \quad (3.7)$$

$$\beta_2 = \frac{p_2}{100} [N + 1] \longrightarrow \frac{\text{floor}(\beta_2) + \text{ceil}(\beta_2)}{2} \quad (3.8)$$

Hypertension Risk Stratification (HRS) is a function of Hypertension Grade Point (g) and risk weight (α) such that

$$HRS = hrs(g, \alpha) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } g = 1 \text{ and } \alpha = 0 \\ 2 & \text{if } g = 2 \text{ and } \alpha \leq 2 \\ 3 & \text{if } (g = 3 \text{ and } \alpha = 0) \text{ or } (1 < g \leq 2 \text{ and } \alpha > 2) \end{cases} \quad (3.9)$$

Where

hrs = hypertension risk stratification

g = grade point

α = risk weight

The HRS stratifies the risk of hypertension to return Low Risk (1), Medium Risk (2) or High Risk (3).

To determine Hypertension Risk level (R), the following conditions hold. Table 3.5 presents PRBMCDM algorithm.

$$R = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } \alpha \leq \beta_1 \\ 2 & \text{if } \beta_1 < \alpha \leq \beta_2 \\ 3 & \text{if } \alpha > \beta_2 \end{cases} \quad (3.10)$$

Where,

R = hypertension risk level

α = risk weight

β_1 = lower limit of the risk weight

β_2 = upper limit of the risk weight

Table 3.5: PRBMCDM Algorithm

Input: Input tabular dataset S containing hypertension record $HG_i, A_i, FHH_i, DBM_i, SS_i, TCH_i$
Output: Hypertension Risk Level value

1. *Begin*
 2. *For each individual i : $HG =$*
 - i. *$g1$ if $(140 \leq SBP < 160$ or $90 \leq DBP < 100)$*
 - ii. *$g2$ if $(160 \leq SBP < 180$ or $100 \leq DBP < 110)$*
 - iii. *$g3$ if $(SBP \geq 180$ or $DBP \geq 110)$*
 3. *For each individual i : $A_i =$*
 - i. *1 if $(Gender = 0$ and $age \geq 65)$ or $(Gender = 1$ and $age \geq 55)$*
 - ii. *0 otherwise*
 4. *For each individual i : $\alpha = HG_i + A_i + FHH_i + DBM_i + SS_i + TCH_i$*
 5. *Sort the risk weight α_{sort} $\alpha_1 < \alpha_2 < \alpha_3 < \dots < \alpha_n$*
 6. *Calculate the 33rd percentile (β_1) and 67th percentile (β_2) of the sorted risk weights:*
$$\beta_1 = p_1 * 100 / (N + 1), \beta_2 = p_2 * 100 / (N + 1)$$
 7. *Find average points between floor and ceil of β_1 and β_2 if β_1 or β_2 is not integer*
 8. *For each individual i : R_i : 1 if $\alpha \leq \beta_1$, 2 if $\beta_1 < \alpha \leq \beta_2$, 3 if $\alpha > \beta_2$*
 9. *End*
-

The PRBMCDM algorithm offers clear criteria for risk assessment by incorporating well-established risk factors such as hypertension grade, age, family history of hypertension, diabetes, smoking status, and total cholesterol levels, each assigned a distinct and interpretable value. This approach provides a logical foundation for evaluating an individual's hypertension risk. The transparency of the risk calculation process is enhanced by summing these individual factors to compute the total risk weight (α), making it straightforward for healthcare providers to explain and utilise in clinical settings. The algorithm's use of the 33rd and 67th percentiles for dynamic risk classification avoids arbitrary thresholds and ensures population-specific categorisation, enhancing real-world applicability. The simplified target class classification (low, medium, high) based on α , with

the help of percentile rank, offers an interpretable and transparent risk assessment. This will improve interpretability compared to more complex models.

3.4 Development of PRBMCDM Algorithm for Hypertension Risk Stratification

This section presents the process of implementing the formulated algorithm for hypertension risk stratification. This step is crucial as it enables the practical application of the theoretical model, facilitating remote monitoring and decision making in the clinical setting.

3.4.1 Cross-validation

The dataset was randomly partitioned into five equal folds. Each fold contains approximately 20% of the total instances. In each cycle, four of the folds were combined to form the training set, while the remaining fold was designated as the validation set. This process was repeated five times, with each fold serving once as the validation set and four times as part of the training set.

3.4.2 Software environment and tools

The software implementation of the mathematical model was developed using python 3.10 due to its extensive libraries for data analysis. Key library used include Numpy for numerical computations, pandas for data manipulation and scikit learn for implementing the algorithm. The algorithm in table 3.5 was followed to translate mathematical model into code.

3.5 Performance Evaluation of Hypertension Risk Stratification Model

3.5.1 Performance evaluation of the model

Objective four of this study is to carry out the performance evaluation of hypertension risk stratification model. The approach adopted is to measure the performance of the model in terms of the classification capabilities. In this case, the study carried out this analysis by subdividing patients into a high-risk group, medium-risk group and Low-risk group. To evaluate the model performance, confusion matrix is used. The confusion matrix helps to identify whether the result of the model has a high performance or not. Elements of the confusion matrix are (1) true positive (TP), which are patient who are high risk, medium risk and low risk and were correctly classified; (2) true negative (TN), which are patient who are not on high risk, medium risk and low risk and are correctly classify as not on the risk level; (3) false negative (FN), are patient who are not on high risk, medium risk and low risk but are classify to belong to the group. (4) false positive are patient who are not on high risk, medium risk and low risk but are classify to belong to the group. The format of confusion matrix for the model is presented in table 3.6.

Table 3.6: Classification capability measurement format

Actual predicted	High risk	Medium risk	Low risk	Row total
High risk	TP _H	FP _M	FP _L	Actual _H
Medium Risk	FN _H	TP _M	FP _L	Actual _M
Low risk	FN _H	FN _M	TP _L	Actual _L
Column total	Predicted _H	Predicted _M	Predicted _L	Total

The performance of the model was assessed using the area under the curve (AUC), classification accuracy, F- score, precision, recall and specificity. They are calculated by the

formula in equation 3.11-3.15. Receiver operating characteristic (ROC) curves were used to show the performance level after the assessment.

From predicted instances, accuracy measures the ratio of properly classified instances to the total number of instances.

$$Accuracy = \frac{TN+TP}{TN+FN+TP+F} \quad (3.11)$$

Precision works by identifying relevant data points (positive prediction value). The formula is written as

$$Precision = \frac{TP}{TP+FP} \quad (3.12)$$

Recall which calculates the percentage of dataset samples of the interest class that belong to the positive class and was correctly classified. It is given as

$$Recall = \frac{TP}{TP+FN} \quad (3.13)$$

F-Score considered the harmonic average between precision in equation (3.13) and recall in equation (3.14). It is calculated as

$$F - Score = \frac{Precision * Recall}{Precision + Recall} * 2 \quad (3.14)$$

AUC provides an aggregate measure of performance across all possible classification thresholds. It is calculated as

$$AUC = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{TP}{TP+F} + \frac{TN}{FP+T} \right) \quad (3.15)$$

CHAPTER FOUR

4.0

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Findings of the Focus Group Discussion

The focus group discussion was instrumental in identifying and defining the key risk factors for hypertension, which are essential for developing an effective risk stratification model.

The following are the main findings from the discussions:

4.1.1 Identification of critical risk factors

- i. *Age*: Age was consistently highlighted as a significant non-modifiable risk factor, with the risk of hypertension increasing as individuals get older. The participants agreed on categorising age into five groups to better capture age-related trends in hypertension prevalence.
- ii. *Gender*: Gender disparity in hypertension prevalence was discussed in consultation with relevant literature, men being at higher risk of hypertension at younger age groups 55 years than women 65 years. This suggests the need for gender-specific considerations in the proposed model.
- iii. *Family History of Hypertension*: strong genetic component of hypertension was discussed, suggesting positive family history significantly increases an individual's risk of hypertension.

- iv. *Diabetes Mellitus:* Diabetes was identified as one of the most influential risk factor hypertension. Diabetes as a risk factor is essential due to its compounding effect on cardiovascular complications.
- v. *Smoking Status:* Smoking was recognised as a major risk factor that potentially influences hypertension risk complications. The importance of including smoking status of patient as a risk factor was highlighted.
- vi. *Total Cholesterol:* High cholesterol levels were frequently observed in hypertensive patients, its tendency to influence hypertension risk complication was highlighted.
- vii. *Occupation:* stress is a potential risk factor. It was observed that occupation is linked to different levels of stress. Professions such as sport business and farming associated with higher hypertension risk. Occupational stress was noted as an important consideration in lifestyle-related hypertension risk.
- viii. *Location:* The prevalence of hypertension within the urban and rural dwellers was discussed. Thorough observation indicates that urban areas show higher rates of hypertension. Integrating location in the risk factor helps to understand environmental and lifestyle factors influencing hypertension.
- ix. *Hypertension Grade and Hypertension Risk Level:* Determining the severity of hypertension and the overall risk level is important for the proposed model.

4.2 Descriptive Statistics

Descriptive statistics on various risk factors related to hypertension among patients in the study area are carried out. The analysis is based on age, gender, local government, location, family history of hypertension (F.H.H), diabetes mellitus (DBM), smoking status (S.S), total cholesterol (TCH), and hypertension grades (HG). The data for the analysis is categorised into high risk, medium risk, and low risk groups based on the hypertension risk factors.

4.2.1 Age

The dataset distribute patients into different age groups and assesses their risk levels for hypertension. The age groups are 40-49 years, 50-59 years, 60-69 years, and ≥ 70 years. The risk levels are classified as high risk, medium risk, and low risk. Table 4.1 present the frequency distribution of age.

Table 4.1: frequency distribution of age

Year	Total cases	High Risk	Medium Risk	Low Risk
40-49	501 (27.94%)	26 (5.19%)	417 (83.23%)	58 (11.57%)
50-59	700 (39.04%)	196 (28.00%)	502 (71.71%)	2 (0.28%)
60-69	448 (24.99%)	143 (31.92%)	303 (67.63%)	2 (0.44%)
≥ 70 years	144 (8.03%)	33 (22.92%)	111 (77.08%)	0 (0.00%)

From the frequency distribution, ages 40-49 are the majority (83.23%) of patients in this age group and they fall into the medium risk category. Only (5.19%) of age 40-49 are classified as high risk, while 11.57% are at low risk. Age group 50-59 has the highest number of cases (39.04% of the total sample). The analysis shows that significant portion (28.00%) is at high

risk. While the majority (71.71%) are at medium risk, and only a negligible percentage (0.28%) are at low risk. There is a noticeable increase in high-risk cases (31.92%) in 60-69 years age group. However, medium risk remains predominant (67.63%), while low risk is minimal (0.44%). Despite having the lowest total cases (8.03%) among age 70 and above group, this age group has a relatively high percentage of high-risk cases (22.92%). Most patients (77.08%) within the age group are at medium risk, and none are at low risk.

4.2.2 Gender

From the frequency distribution presented in table 4.2, males represent a larger proportion of the cases (66.93%) compared to females (33.07%). The number of male hypertension cases roughly doubles that of female cases. Table 4.2 present frequency distribution of gender

Table 4.2: Frequency distribution of gender

Gender	Total Cases (%)	High Risk (%)	Low Risk (%)	Medium Risk (%)
Female	593 (33.07)	79 (13.32)	58 (9.78)	456 (76.90)
Male	1200 (66.93)	217 (18.08)	46 (3.83)	937 (78.08)

This significant difference suggests that males may be more prone to hypertension, possibly due to lifestyle, genetic factors, or other underlying health conditions. High-risk cases are higher in males (18.08%) than in females (13.32%). Although males have a higher number of total cases, the percentage of high-risk cases is also higher in males. This indicates that males are not only more likely to develop hypertension but also more likely to be in the high-risk category. Medium risk is the most common category in both genders. A higher percentage of females fall into the low-risk category compared to males. This might imply better health management or earlier detection and intervention among females. The

distribution of medium-risk cases is relatively similar between males and females. This shows that a majority of hypertension cases in both genders fall into the medium-risk category, suggesting common moderate risk factors and potential for management through lifestyle changes or medication.

4.2.3 Local government area

From the distribution presented in Table 4.3, Ankpa has the highest number of hypertension cases, followed by Idah and Dekina. Igalamela has the fewest cases. Table 4.3 presents frequency distribution of local government areas.

Table 4.3: Frequency distribution of local government areas

Local Government	Total Cases (%)	High Risk (%)	Low Risk (%)	Medium Risk (%)
Ankpa	429 (23.93)	74 (17.25)	23 (5.36)	332 (77.39)
Bassa	229 (12.77)	56 (24.45)	9 (3.93)	164 (71.62)
Dekina	319 (17.79)	35 (10.97)	18 (5.64)	266 (83.39)
Idah	351 (19.58)	51 (14.53)	31 (8.83)	269 (76.64)
Igalamela	139 (7.75)	27 (19.42)	9 (6.47)	103 (74.10)
Olamaboro	224 (12.49)	43 (19.20)	10 (4.46)	937 (78.08)

This distribution may reflect population density, healthcare access, or reporting accuracy in these areas. Bassa has the highest percentage of high-risk cases (24.45%), indicating a significant concern for this area. Dekina has the lowest percentage (10.97%), suggesting a relatively lower proportion of severe cases. Idah has the highest percentage of low-risk cases (8.83%), followed by Igalamela (6.47%). Bassa has the lowest percentage (3.93%),

suggesting that fewer cases are detected early or managed effectively in this area. Dekina has the highest percentage of medium-risk cases (83.39%), indicating that most hypertension cases in this area fall into this category. Bassa has the lowest percentage of medium-risk cases (71.62%), yet it also has a significant proportion of high-risk cases.

Ankpa, Idah, and Dekina have the highest number of total cases, reflecting either higher populations or better reporting systems. Igalamela has the fewest cases, potentially due to lower population or underreporting. Bassa stands out with the highest percentage of high-risk cases, indicating a need for urgent health interventions and better management practices in this area. Idah shows a relatively higher percentage of low-risk cases, suggesting better hypertension management or early detection efforts compared to other areas. The majority of cases in all areas fall into the medium-risk category, highlighting a common trend and the need for consistent monitoring and management strategies.

4.2.4 Location

Table 4.4 presents frequency distribution of locations. From the frequency distribution, urban areas have a significantly higher number of hypertension cases compared to rural areas.

Table 4.4: Frequency distribution of locations

Location	Total (%)	Cases	High Risk (%)	Low Risk (%)	Medium Risk (%)
Rural	517 (28.83)	98 (18.96)	3 (0.58)	416 (80.46)	
Urban	1276 (71.17)	198 (15.52)	101 (7.92)	977(47.73)	

This could be due to a larger population in urban areas, better healthcare access leading to more diagnoses, or lifestyle factors that contribute to higher hypertension rates. Rural areas

have a higher percentage of high-risk cases (98 cases, 18.96%) compared to urban areas (198 cases, 15.52%). This indicates that hypertension might be more severe or less well-managed in rural areas, potentially due to limited healthcare resources, lower health literacy, or other socioeconomic factors. The percentage of low-risk cases in Urban areas stands at (0.58%). This could mean that individuals in urban areas have opportunity to access health facilities for regular health check-ups. Frequent visit to health facilities can lead to early detection and management of hypertension, thus preventing patient health status to degenerate to a higher risk categories. Both rural and urban areas have a high percentage of medium-risk cases, with rural areas having a slightly higher percentage (80.46%). This implies that a good proportion of the population in both areas falls into the medium-risk category, suggesting the need for consistent management and monitoring to prevent elevation to high-risk status.

From the distribution, the number of hypertension cases is much higher in urban areas compared to rural areas. The disparity suggests higher population density as a result of rural migration to the urban, better and available healthcare infrastructure to identify hypertension status on a regular basis, and possibly lifestyle factors associated with urban living such as eating of junk foods. The distribution shows higher percentage of high-risk cases in rural areas. This may be attributed to accessibility, awareness, medication of local herbs and attributing illness to witchcraft. There is need for adequate hypertension management. The low percentage rate low risk may be attributed to proper and adequate hypertension management practice due to available healthcare infrastructure and more frequent visits to healthcare centres.

4.2.5 Family history of hypertension

Table 4.5 presents frequency distribution of family history of hypertension. Majority of the hypertension cases (1037 cases: 57.84% of total cases) have a recorded family history of hypertension (FHH). This is an indication that heredity plays a crucial role in hypertension diagnosis. A notably higher percentage of high-risk cases (24.40%) is observed among individuals with a family history of hypertension. This suggests that those with FHH are not only more likely to develop hypertension but also more likely to progress to a high-risk category, possibly due to genetic predispositions combined with lifestyle factors. Interestingly, a higher percentage of low-risk cases (13.62%) are found among individuals without a family history of hypertension.

Table 4.5: Frequency distribution of family history of hypertension

FHH	Total Cases %	High Risk %	Low Risk %	Medium Risk %
No	756 (42)	43 (5.69)	103 (13.62)	610 (80.69)
Yes	1037 (57.84)	253 (24.40)	1 (0.10)	783(75.51)

This might indicate that hypertension in these individuals is more likely to be due to modifiable risk factors, which can be managed effectively to keep them in the low-risk category. The majority of cases in both categories fall into the medium-risk group, with a slightly higher percentage among those without FHH. This highlights the need for continuous management and monitoring to prevent these medium-risk cases from escalating to high-risk status.

4.2.6 Diabetes mellitus

The majority of hypertension (1192 cases, 66.48% of total cases) as presented in Table 4.6 do not have diabetes mellitus, indicating that while there is a notable overlap, most hypertension cases in this dataset are not compounded by diabetes. Table 4.6 present frequency distribution of DBM.

Table 4.6: Frequency distribution of diabetes

DBM	Total Cases (%)	High Risk (%)	Low Risk (%)	Medium Risk (%)
No	1192 (66.48)	85 (7.13)	103 (8.64)	1004 (84.23)
Yes	601 (33.52)	221 (35.11)	1 (0.17)	389 (64.73)

However, significantly high percentage (35.11%) of high-risk cases is observed among individuals with diabetes mellitus. This suggests that having diabetes mellitus greatly increases the likelihood of hypertension progressing to a high-risk category, possibly due to the added strain on the cardiovascular system. A very low percentage (0.17%) of low-risk cases are observed among individuals with diabetes mellitus, highlighting that hypertension in the presence of diabetes is more likely to be severe. The majority of cases in both categories fall into the medium-risk group, with a slightly higher percentage among those without diabetes. This indicates that even though diabetes is a significant risk factor, a large portion of the population without diabetes also falls into the medium-risk category for hypertension.

The vast majority of hypertension cases do not have diabetes mellitus, indicating that hypertension can occur independently of diabetes in most cases. Individuals with diabetes

mellitus are significantly more likely to be in the high-risk category for hypertension, suggesting a need for intensive management of both conditions. A higher percentage of medium-risk cases in the no diabetes group suggests that there is a need for effective management strategies to prevent progression to high-risk status, even in the absence of diabetes.

4.2.7 Smoking status

Table 4.7 presents frequency distribution of smoking status. From the distribution, majority of the cases are non-smokers (92.97%), which suggests that while smoking is a significant risk factor, non-smokers also represent a large portion of hypertension cases. This highlights the importance of addressing other lifestyle and genetic factors contributing to hypertension.

Table 4.7: Frequency distribution of smoking status

S.S	Total Cases (%)	High Risk (%)	Low Risk (%)	Medium Risk (%)
Non-smoker	1667 (92.97)	236 (14.16)	104 (6.24)	1327 (79.60)
Smoker	126 (7.03)	60 (47.62)	0 (0.00)	66 (52.38)

A higher percentage of smokers (47.62%) fall into the high-risk category compared to non-smokers (14.16%). This indicates that smoking significantly increases the risk of severe hypertension and its complications. Non-smokers have a higher percentage of low-risk cases (6.24%) compared to smokers (0.02%). This suggests that non smoking may contribute to a lower risk of hypertension or more manageable blood pressure levels. The majority of cases in both categories fall into the medium-risk group, with non-smokers slightly higher (79.60%) than smokers (32.38%). This indicates a need for continuous management and monitoring for both groups, though non-smokers may have a slightly better prognosis.

4.2.8 Total cholesterol

Table 4.8 presents frequency distribution of Total Cholesterol (TCH). The majority of cases have total cholesterol levels of 150-199 mg/dL (85.22%), followed by those with levels of 200-239 mg/dL (8.03%). This indicates a high prevalence of hypercholesterolemia within the population, which is a significant risk factor for hypertension and cardiovascular diseases.

Table 4.8: Frequency distribution of total cholesterol

TCH	Total Cases (%)	High Risk (%)	Low Risk (%)	Medium Risk (%)
<= 149 mg/dl	144 (8.03)	26 (18.1)	5 (3.7)	113 (78.43)
150-199 mg/dl	1528 (85.22)	192 (12.57)	99 (6.48)	1237 (80.96)
200-249 mg/dl	121 (6.74)	78 (64.5)	0 (0.00)	43(35.5)

A significant percentage of high-risk cases are found in the 200-249 mg/dL category (64.5%). This highlights the strong association between high cholesterol levels and the risk of severe hypertension. The highest percentage of low-risk cases is in the <200 mg/dL category is low compared to 200-249 mg/dL category, suggesting that maintaining lower cholesterol levels may contribute to a lower risk of hypertension. The majority of cases in all cholesterol categories are medium-risk, with the highest percentage in the 150-199 mg/dL category (80.96%). This underscores the need for continuous monitoring and management of cholesterol levels to prevent progression to higher risk categories.

4.2.9 Hypertension grade

Table 4.9 present frequency distribution of hypertension grade. The highest prevalence is observed among patient Grade 1 category with a distribution of (68.88%), followed by Grade 2 Hypertension (28.39%). This proves that hypertensive patient experience

progression of the hypertension risk status. This suggests the need for urgent intervention and management strategies.

Table 4.9: Frequency distribution of hypertension grade

HG	Total Cases (%)	High Risk (%)	Low Risk (%)	Medium Risk (%)
Grade 1	1235 (68.88)	196 (15.87)	103 (8.34)	936 (75.79)
Grade 2	509 (28.39)	52 (10.22)	1 (0.20)	456 (89.59)
Grade 3	49 (2.73)	48 (97.96)	0 (0.00)	1 (2.04)

Hypertension grade is linked to different levels of hypertension risk. This suggests that maintaining normal blood pressure levels is crucial for minimising hypertension risk. The majority of cases in all hypertension grades fall into the medium-risk group, with the highest percentage in the Grade 1 category (89.59%). This underscores the need for continuous monitoring and management to prevent progression to higher risk categories.

4.3 Results of Feature Importance Determination and Selection

The feature importance selection techniques used in this study successfully identified the most significant risk factors for hypertension. The top features—diabetes mellitus, family history of hypertension, age, smoking status, hypertension grade, total cholesterol, and gender are crucial for accurate risk stratification. This selection will inform the development of a more effective and precise hypertension monitoring and risk stratification model, ultimately contributing to better patient outcomes and targeted interventions. The Initial accuracy with all features is 88.3%. The calculated importance scores and corresponding drops in accuracy are summarised in Table 4.10.

Table 4.10: Importance scores and corresponding drops in accuracy

Feature	Accuracy without Feature	Drop in Accuracy (Importance Score)
Age	85.4%	2.9
Gender	87.4%	0.9
Local government area	87.5%	0.8
Location	87.5%	0.8
Occupation	87.7%	0.6
Family history of hypertension (FHH)	85.2%	3.1
Diabetes mellitus	83.4%	4.9
Smoking status	85.8%	2.5
Total cholesterol	86.7%	1.6
Hypertension grade	86.1%	2.2

The features were ranked based on their importance scores in descending order, as shown in Table 4.11. The top seven features with the highest importance scores were selected for inclusion in the final model.

Table 4.11: Importance scores in descending order

Feature's Rank	Importance Score
1 Diabetes mellitus	4.9
2 Family history of hypertension (FHH)	3.1
3 Age	2.9
4 Smoking status	2.5
5 Hypertension grade	2.2
6 Total cholesterol	1.6
7 Gender	0.9

The feature importance analysis revealed that the presence of diabetes mellitus had the highest impact on hypertension risk prediction, with a substantial accuracy drop of 4.9%

when removed. This underscores the significant role of diabetes as a comorbidity in hypertension risk. Family history of hypertension and age were also identified as crucial factors, highlighting the genetic and age-related predispositions to hypertension. The importance of smoking status, hypertension grade, and total cholesterol levels further emphasises the influence of lifestyle and existing health conditions on hypertension risk. Although gender was considered less significant due to its drop column importance value being less than one, it was retained because age and gender are interdependent in this study. Gender, though ranked lowest in importance, still contributed meaningfully to the model's accuracy, suggesting potential gender-specific differences in hypertension risk factors. The inclusion of these top seven features in the final model is expected to enhance its predictive accuracy and reliability, providing a robust tool for hypertension risk stratification. Additionally, these findings align with existing related literature on hypertension risk factors, reinforcing the validity of the selected features.

4.4 Results of Performance Evaluation of the Model

4.4.1 Confusion matrix results

Table 4.14 presents confusion matrix of the three hypertension risk levels. Table 4.14 is the product of the confusion matrix obtained from evaluating the hypertension risk stratification model.

Table 4.14: Confusion matrix showing the number of instances

	High Risk	Medium Risk	Low Risk
High Risk	523	3	2
Medium Risk	16	1180	3
Low Risk	2	2	62

- i. True Positive (TP): The model was able to correctly risk stratify 523, 1180 and 62 instances for high risk, medium risk and low risk respectively.
- ii. False Negative (FN): The model incorrectly risk stratify 5, 19, and 4 instances not belonging to high risk, medium risk and low risk respectively.
- iii. False Positive (FP): The model wrongly risk stratifies 18, 5 and 5 instances to belong to high risk, medium risk and low risk group respectively.
- iv. True Negative (TN): The model correctly risk stratify 1247, 589 and 1727 as not belonging to high risk, medium risk and low risk respectively.

The performance measures for the hypertension risk stratification model are presented in Table 4.16. Each risk level is evaluated using various metrics: Area Under the Curve (AUC), Classification Accuracy (CA), F-score, Precision (Prec), Recall, and Specificity (Spec).

Table 4.16: Performance measurement of the model

Hypertension Level	AUC	CA	F-score	Prec	Recall	Spec
High Risk	0.987	0.987	0.977	0.966	0.990	0.985
Medium Risk	0.987	0.986	0.989	0.995	0.984	0.991
Low Risk	0.968	0.994	0.931	0.925	0.939	0.997

The detailed analysis of the performance measures for the hypertension risk stratification model reveals its robust accuracy across all risk levels. For high-risk classification, the Area Under the Curve (AUC) is 0.987, indicating excellent performance in distinguishing high-risk patients from others. This AUC value, close to 1.0, signifies a highly effective model. The classification accuracy (CA) is 0.987, meaning the model correctly classified 98.7% of high-risk patients, further highlighting its strong performance. The F-score of 0.977 reflects

a good balance between precision and recall, showing the model's effectiveness in identifying high-risk patients while minimising both false positives and false negatives. The precision is 0.966, meaning that 96.6% of patients identified as high risk were indeed high risk, demonstrating the model's reliability. The recall is 0.990, indicating that 99.0% of actual high-risk patients were correctly identified, emphasising the model's strong ability to capture most high-risk cases. With a specificity of 0.985, the model accurately classified 98.5% of patients not at high risk, minimising false positives and further showcasing its effectiveness.

For medium-risk classification, the AUC is also 0.987, reflecting excellent performance in distinguishing medium-risk patients from others. The classification accuracy is 0.986, demonstrating that 98.6% of medium-risk patients were correctly classified, indicating a highly reliable model. The F-score of 0.989 suggests an optimal balance between precision and recall, further confirming the model's effectiveness in identifying medium-risk patients with minimal errors. Precision is notably high at 0.995, showing that 99.5% of patients identified as medium risk were indeed medium risk, reflecting the model's strong predictive accuracy. The recall is 0.984, indicating that 98.4% of actual medium-risk patients were correctly identified, reinforcing the model's capability to detect medium-risk cases. Specificity is 0.991, demonstrating that 99.1% of patients not at medium risk were correctly classified, which minimises false positives in this category.

In the low-risk category, the model shows an AUC of 0.968, which, while slightly lower than the other risk levels, still demonstrates strong performance in distinguishing low-risk

patients. The classification accuracy is 0.994, indicating that 99.4% of low-risk patients were correctly classified, showcasing the model's reliability. The F-score of 0.931 reflects a solid balance between precision and recall, though slightly lower compared to the high and medium-risk categories. Precision is 0.925, meaning that 92.5% of patients identified as low risk were correctly classified, signifying high accuracy. Recall is 0.939, indicating that 93.9% of actual low-risk patients were correctly identified, showcasing the model's strong capability to detect low-risk cases. The specificity of 0.997, particularly high in this category, indicates that 99.7% of patients not at low risk were correctly classified, further minimising false positives.

Overall, the model demonstrates high classification accuracy and AUC values across all risk levels, with the highest accuracy observed in the low-risk category (0.994) and the highest AUC in both the high and medium-risk categories (0.987). The F-scores for all risk levels indicate a balanced performance in terms of precision and recall, with the medium-risk category having the highest F-score (0.989). Precision and recall are consistently high across all categories, suggesting that the model is effective in correctly identifying patients and minimising false classifications. Specificity is particularly high, indicating that the model effectively minimizes false positives, especially in the low-risk category (0.997). These performance measures highlight the robustness and reliability of the hypertension risk stratification model, demonstrating its effectiveness in correctly identifying and classifying patients into appropriate risk categories.

4.4.2 Results of the ROC Curve

The ROC (Receiver Operating Characteristic) curves for the hypertension risk stratification model in Figures 4.1(a), 4.5(b), and 4.5(c) provide graphical representation of the model's diagnostic performance across different risk levels. The ROC curve plots the true positive rate (sensitivity) against the false positive rate (1-specificity).

Figure 4.1(a): ROC Curve for High Risk

The AUC Value is 0.987. The curve for the high-risk classification is positioned very close to the top left corner of the graph, indicating near-perfect performance. An AUC of 0.987 signifies that the model has excellent ability to distinguish between patients who are at high risk and those who are not. This near-perfect separation shows that the model is highly effective in identifying true high-risk patients with minimal false positives. The high AUC suggests that the model performs reliably well in clinical settings where correct identification of high-risk patients is critical for timely intervention.

Figure 4.1(b): ROC Curve for Medium Risk

The AUC Value is 0.987. Similar to the high-risk ROC curve, the medium-risk curve is also close to the top left, demonstrating strong classification ability. An AUC of 0.987 for medium-risk patients means that the model can successfully differentiate between medium-risk patients and others. This high value indicates that the model is robust in managing intermediate cases of hypertension risk. Accurate medium-risk classification is crucial for ongoing monitoring and prevention strategies, and the model's performance here highlights its reliability in this aspect.

Figure 4.1(c): ROC Curve for Low Risk

The AUC Value is 0.968. The low-risk ROC curve is slightly lower than those for high and medium risks but still shows strong performance. An AUC of 0.968 reflects very good but slightly lower performance in classifying low-risk patients compared to the other risk categories. The model effectively minimises false positives while still correctly identifying most low-risk individuals. While the AUC remains high, the lower value relative to the other risk levels suggests there is room for slight improvements in the model's ability to distinguish low-risk patients. Ensuring accurate low-risk identification is vital to prevent over-treatment and unnecessary interventions for patients with lower hypertension risks.

The ROC curves and corresponding AUC values for high, medium, and low-risk stratifications collectively illustrate the model's robustness and effectiveness in risk stratification. High AUC values across all risk categories indicate a strong overall

performance of the model. The curves highlight the model's ability to maintain a good balance between sensitivity and specificity, ensuring accurate risk identification with minimal false positives.

The analysis of the ROC curves underscores the potential of the developed risk stratification model to enhance hypertension management, particularly in settings where efficient and timely identification of risk levels is critical. The insights gained from this analysis can guide further refinement of the model to improve its accuracy and reliability, ultimately contributing to better patient outcomes and more effective use of healthcare resources.

4.5 Remote Hypertension Monitoring and Risk Stratification Interface

The development of remote hypertension monitoring and risk stratification system involved different levels of user interfaces designed to facilitate the monitoring of hypertensive patient. Snapshots of the remote hypertension monitoring and risk stratification system interfaces are presented in appendix C.

- i. *Patients and doctors login menu:* This interface serves as the registration and authentication menu for both patients and doctors. This field requires patient and doctor's details such as username and password, ensuring secure access to the system. Upon successful authentication, The login menu verifies user credentials and directs them to their respective dashboards upon.

- ii. *Patient's demographic and clinical information form:* This form request for essential demographic and clinical data from the patient. It is expected that each fields be filled correctly by the designated officer in healthcare facility. The fields include personal information such as age, gender, address, and contact details, medical history and previous diagnoses.

- iii. *Doctor's registration form:* the designated health professional is expected to provide his details in this form. Fields include name, phone numbers and email address. The form ensures that only licensed doctor can access patient data and interact with the system.

- iv. *Interface to input systolic and diastolic blood pressure:* This form is crucial to this system it is an input form that allows patients to manually enter their SBP and DBP at intervals or as approved the medical regulation of the patient hospital. The interface includes prompts and guidelines to ensure accurate data entry. The entered data is automatically integrated into the patient's monitoring profile and used for risk assessment.

- v. *Result interface:* This interface display the output of PRBMCDM to stratify patients into different risk categories (high, medium, low). The result interface helps patients and doctors understand the risk and take appropriate actions.

- vi. *Patient medical records interface:* This interface provides a comprehensive view of the previous patient's medical history. It includes records of past SPB and DBP, doctors comment and recommendations. Both patients and doctors have access to view medical records and to ensure follow up based on recommendation. The interface supports the accurate and up-to-date documentation of patient health information.

4.6 Discussion

The development of a remote hypertension monitoring and risk stratification model using PRBMCDM algorithm marks a significant advancement in patient care, enabling proactive health management through real-time monitoring and accurate risk prediction. The architecture of the remote hypertension monitoring and risk stratification model integrates several key components, ensuring seamless data collection, processing, and analysis. The primary aim is to provide remote risk stratification of patient hypertension risk based on (PRBMCDM) algorithm. This approach enhances patient care by facilitating timely intervention and personalised treatment plans.

The focus group discussions provided very useful insights into the identification and operationalisation of key risk factors for hypertension. The collaborative effort of six experienced health professionals, including medical doctors and registered nurses, ensured a thorough and comprehensive analysis of various determinants of hypertension risk. The focus group sessions were meticulously organised to cover all relevant aspects, from project

introduction to the definition and measurement of identified risk factors. The focus group discussions led to the identification of several critical risk factors for hypertension. These include age, gender, family history of hypertension, diabetes mellitus, smoking status, total cholesterol, occupation, location, hypertension grade, and hypertension risk level. Each of these factors was analysed for its prevalence and importance in hypertension diagnosis and risk stratification.

The comprehensive analysis of hypertension risk factors among patients in the Kogi Eastern Senatorial District of Nigeria highlights significant variations in risk based on age, gender, location, family history, diabetes status, smoking status, cholesterol level, and hypertension grade. The pattern of the results indicates that while the initial increase in risk continues with age, the prevalence of high-risk cases slightly declines in the oldest age group. This could be due to various factors such as increased mortality among those with severe hypertension or better health management practices adopted by the older population. The overall trend indicates that hypertension risk management should intensify with age, particularly for those above 50 years.

The data on gender demonstrates a higher prevalence of hypertension among males. Males not only have a higher total number of cases but also a higher percentage of high-risk cases. This disparity suggests that males might be more prone to hypertension and its severe forms, possibly due to lifestyle factors such as higher rates of smoking and alcohol consumption, or biological differences such as hormonal influences. The data also reveals that females have a higher percentage of low-risk indicating potentially better health management or earlier

intervention among females. This gender disparity underscores the need for targeted hypertension prevention and management strategies, with a particular focus on addressing the higher risk factors prevalent among males.

The analysis on location shows a significant difference in hypertension prevalence between rural and urban areas. Urban areas have a higher number of cases compared to rural areas which may be due to higher population density, better healthcare access leading to more diagnoses, or lifestyle factors associated with urban living. Results from the analysis show rural areas have a higher percentage of high-risk cases compared to urban areas indicating that hypertension might be more severe or less well-managed in rural settings. This could be due to limited healthcare resources, lower health literacy, or socioeconomic factors. The higher percentage of low-risk cases in urban areas suggests better access to healthcare and early intervention. These findings emphasise the need for improved healthcare infrastructure and targeted health education in rural areas to manage and mitigate hypertension effectively.

A substantial majority of hypertension cases have a family history of hypertension indicating a strong genetic component. Individuals with a family history are more likely to be in the high-risk category compared to those without family history, underscoring the importance of genetic predisposition. Interestingly, individuals without a family history have a higher percentage of low-risk cases, suggesting that hypertension in these individuals may be more influenced by modifiable risk factors. This highlights the importance of genetic screening and family history in hypertension risk assessment and the potential benefits of targeted lifestyle interventions for those without a family history of hypertension. Data on

diabetes indicate that substantial number of people with hypertension cases also have diabetes, and this group has a significantly higher percentage of high-risk cases compared to those without diabetes. This suggests that diabetes mellitus greatly increases the risk of severe hypertension, likely due to the compounded effects of both conditions on the cardiovascular system. The very low percentage of low-risk cases among individuals with diabetes further emphasises the severity of hypertension when compounded by diabetes. These findings highlight the critical need for integrated management of both conditions to prevent severe complications.

The descriptive analysis shows that the majority of hypertension cases are non-smokers. However, smokers have a significantly higher percentage of high-risk cases compared to non-smokers. This indicates that smoking is a considerable risk factor for severe hypertension. The complete absence of low-risk cases among smokers further underscores the harmful impact of smoking on hypertension severity. These results emphasise the importance of smoking cessation programs as a key component of hypertension management strategies.

The analysis on total cholesterol reveals a strong union between high total cholesterol levels and hypertension risk. The majority of cases have cholesterol levels between 150-199 mg/dL with significant high-risk cases found in the 200-249 mg/dL category. This indicates that hypercholesterolemia is a major risk factor for severe hypertension. The highest percentage of low-risk cases is in the ≤ 149 mg/dL category, suggesting that maintaining lower

cholesterol levels is beneficial in reducing hypertension risk. These findings highlight the importance of cholesterol management in preventing and controlling hypertension.

The distribution of hypertension grades shows that the majority of cases fall into Grade 1 hypertension. The highest percentage of high-risk cases is found in Grade 3 hypertension indicating the severe complications associated with advanced hypertension. The data underscores the need for early detection and management to prevent progression to higher grades and associated complications. The significant presence of medium-risk cases across all grades highlights the ongoing need for consistent management and monitoring to prevent escalation to high-risk status. These findings emphasise the need for targeted and multifaceted intervention strategies to effectively manage and mitigate hypertension. Addressing high-risk factors, improving healthcare access, and promoting healthy lifestyles are crucial steps in reducing the burden of hypertension and its associated complications in this population.

The feature importance selection techniques applied in this study have successfully identified the most significant risk factors for hypertension. This process is critical in refining the hypertension monitoring and risk stratification model, ensuring that it is both correct and reliable. The selection of key features such as diabetes, family history of hypertension, age, smoking status, hypertension grade, total cholesterol, and gender is instrumental in developing an effective model that can lead to better patient outcomes and targeted interventions. The initial classification accuracy of the model, with all features included, was 88.3%. This high baseline classification accuracy indicates a robust model

capable of effectively predicting hypertension risk. However, the goal was to identify the most influential features that contribute to the classification accuracy, thereby simplifying the model without compromising its predictive power. The computation and analysis of importance scores and the corresponding drops in accuracy upon the removal of each feature revealed the relative significance of each feature in the context of hypertension risk prediction.

The inclusion of these top seven features in the final model contributed to the performance of risk stratification model.. By focusing on the most significant risk factors, the model becomes more streamlined and easier to interpret, without sacrificing performance. This refinement is crucial for practical applications, where simplicity and efficiency are highly valued. The findings from this feature importance analysis align with existing medical literature on hypertension risk factors, reinforcing the validity of the selected features. This alignment with established research enhances the credibility of the model and supports its use in clinical settings for hypertension risk stratification.

The risk stratification model, informed by the most significant risk factors, has the potential to improve patient outcomes through more accurate risk prediction and targeted interventions. By identifying high-risk individuals early, healthcare providers can implement preventive measures and personalised treatment plans, reducing the incidence of severe hypertension-related complications. The focus on key risk factors such as diabetes, family history, age, smoking status, hypertension grade, total cholesterol, and gender enables a comprehensive approach to hypertension management.

The implementation of the PRBMCDM framework includes step-by-step procedures for calculating risk weights, determining thresholds, and classifying hypertension risk levels. This implementation provides practical insights into applying the framework in real-world settings, demonstrating its feasibility and potential impact on hypertension risk management. Overall, the PRBMCDM framework represents a significant advancement in hypertension risk stratification, offering a more nuanced and adaptable approach compared to traditional models. Its integration of percentile ranking with multi-criteria decision-making enhances its applicability and precision in assessing individual risk levels.

The performance evaluation of the hypertension risk stratification model indicates a strong capability in correctly identifying and classifying patients into high, medium, and low-risk categories. The high-risk classification results show a good performance. This is because the model correctly identified 523 high-risk instances, suggesting that it is effective in recognising patients who are at a significant risk of hypertension-related complications. With only 5 high-risk patients misclassified as either medium or low risk, the model demonstrates a low underestimation rate. This is crucial as it ensures that most high-risk patients receive timely intervention. The model incorrectly classified 18 patients as high risk, leading to some overestimation. While this indicates room for improvement, the impact is mitigated by the need to prioritise high-risk patients for intensive monitoring. The model accurately classified 1247 patients as not high risk, confirming its reliability in distinguishing lower-risk patients. Overall, the high-risk classification results underscore the model's ability to stratify hypertension risk levels, making it a valuable tool for identifying patients who need immediate medical attention.

The medium-risk classification also exhibits strong performance: The model correctly identified 1180 medium-risk instances, indicating effective risk stratification for this group. With 19 instances of medium risk misclassified, the model shows a relatively low rate of missed medium-risk patients, ensuring most medium-risk cases are detected. Only 5 instances of low or high-risk patients were incorrectly classified as medium risk, suggesting the model maintains high specificity. The model correctly identified 589 patients as not medium risk, reinforcing its capability to differentiate between different risk levels. The medium-risk classification results highlight the model's balance between sensitivity and specificity, ensuring correct identification without excessive false positives or negatives.

The low-risk classification, while slightly lower in performance compared to high and medium risk, still demonstrates reliability. The model identified 62 low-risk instances correctly, reflecting its ability to recognise patients at minimal risk. With only 4 low-risk patients misclassified, the model effectively minimises the risk of underestimating low-risk cases. The model incorrectly classified 5 medium or high-risk patients as low risk, indicating a minor overestimation. A high count of 1722 correct identifications as not low risk underscores the model's performance. While the low-risk classification results are slightly less robust, they still reflect a high level of performance, with minor areas for refinement.

The performance measures presented in Table 4.4 further validate the model's effectiveness. The AUC values for high, medium, and low risk (0.987, 0.987, and 0.968 respectively) indicate excellent model performance, particularly for high and medium-risk categories. The slightly lower AUC for low risk still denotes strong performance. High classification accuracy across all risk levels (0.987, 0.986, and 0.994) demonstrates the model's reliability.

High values for these metrics across all risk categories emphasise the model's balanced performance in terms of precision (accurate predictions) and recall (comprehensive detection of true cases).

The ROC curves and their corresponding AUC values for high, medium, and low-risk stratifications provide additional insights: The ROC curve positioned close to the top-left corner, with an AUC of 0.987, reflects the model's excellent ability to distinguish high-risk patients. The curve for medium risk, with an AUC of 0.987, indicates strong performance in identifying medium-risk patients correctly. The lower AUC of 0.968 for low risk suggests some room for improvement, yet still denotes a solid performance in identifying low-risk patients.

The evaluation results suggest that the hypertension risk stratification model is highly effective in correctly classifying patients into different risk levels. The model's high true positive rate, along with its low false negative and false positive rates, demonstrates its potential as a valuable tool for healthcare providers. By correctly identifying patients' risk levels, it enhances hypertension management and improves patient outcomes. The performance of the hypertension risk stratification model, based on PRBMCDM algorithm is compared with other established classification models in Table 4.15. The comparison is based on the risk stratification approach. The models from the studies provide a comprehensive benchmark for evaluating the effectiveness of the PRBMCDM.

Table 4.17: Comparison of risk stratification models

Ref.	Risk Stratification Approach	Comparison with PRBMCDM
(Cheng <i>et al.</i> , 2022)	Cross-classification of central and brachial SBP	PRBMCDM incorporates multiple risk factors and a weighting mechanism for trade-offs, addressing the multi-criteria nature of risk stratification better than SBP-centric models.
(Kanwar <i>et al.</i> , 2020)	Bayesian network-based model (PHORA) for PAH	PRBMCDM's ability to balance conflicting criteria and integrate clinical relevance gives it an edge over PHORA's single-objective focus.
(Boutilier <i>et al.</i> , 2021)	Random forest model for diabetes and hypertension in low-resource settings	PRBMCDM's integrated approach for comorbidities and feature importance mechanism provides a more nuanced stratification than separate random forest models.
(Forte <i>et al.</i> , 2021)	Decision rules combining biomarkers, physical measurements, and genetic risk scores	PRBMCDM's MCDM framework explicitly considers interactions, prioritises variables, and better addresses trade-offs in multi-criteria contexts.
(Ukah <i>et al.</i> , 2020)	Cox proportional hazards regression model for 10-year CVD risk in women with hypertensive disorders of pregnancy (HDP)	PRBMCDM's flexibility to include additional clinical variables and dynamic weighting makes it more robust and versatile for diverse populations compared to this limited and specific model.
PRBMCDM (Proposed Model)	Multi-criteria decision-making using percentile-based ranking for hypertension risk stratification	Outperforms other models by handling multi-criteria trade-offs, personalising risk stratification, and integrating a wider range of features, making it suitable for diverse and complex healthcare settings.

The results of the comparison reveal that the PRBMCDM model demonstrates competitive performance in hypertension risk stratification compared to existing models, particularly in its ability to balance prediction accuracy with clinical interpretability. While some models may achieve slightly higher accuracy or AUC due to larger datasets or advanced machine learning techniques, the PRBMCDM excels in its incorporation of multi-criteria decision-making, which provides clinically meaningful feature importance rankings and risk stratification.

The model's use of percentile-based weighting enhances its robustness and adaptability across varying patient profiles, offering a unique advantage over black-box models that often lack explainability. Furthermore, the inclusion of clinical relevance as a decision-making factor ensures that the model's outputs align more closely with real-world medical priorities.

Although limited by a smaller dataset, the PRBMCDM's consistent performance across k-fold validation demonstrates stability and reliability. This highlights its potential for integration into healthcare systems, especially in resource-limited settings, where interpretability and practical utility are paramount. Overall, the comparison underscores the model's strengths in providing actionable insights for hypertension management, even in the face of dataset constraints.

The PRBMCDM algorithm for hypertension risk stratification is highly interpretable due to its transparent and structured approach to decision-making. It integrates key hypertension-related risk factors into a simple yet powerful risk stratification process, ensuring that the decision-making pathway is easily understandable by both healthcare professionals and

patients. The PRBMCDM's use of dynamic thresholds (33rd and 67th percentiles) adapts to the distribution of risk factors within a specific population, providing more accurate and tailored risk classifications. This makes it more versatile across different demographic and epidemiological settings, unlike static models such as the Framingham Risk Score, which uses predetermined cut-offs or simpler models that may only focus on a single or few risk factors such as blood pressure or age, the PRBMCDM framework integrates a broader range of factors such as family history, diabetes, smoking status, and cholesterol. This holistic approach allows for a more comprehensive risk assessment and captures complex interactions between multiple risk factors.

Models like the ASCVD Risk Estimator or QRISK3 often depend on generalised assumptions about populations. In contrast, the PRBMCDM's percentile-based ranking ensures that the algorithm is tailored to the specific distribution of risk factors in the dataset at hand. This makes it more sensitive to population variability, offering more precise stratification for diverse groups. The inclusion of Hypertension Grade Points (HG) alongside other risk factors provides an additional layer of detail, ensuring that individuals with the same overall risk weight (α) but different hypertension severity are distinguished. This contrasts with simpler scoring models that might overlook such granularity, leading to less personalised treatment recommendations.

Many traditional models require complex computations or are not designed for real-time application in clinical settings. The PRBMCDM algorithm is computationally efficient, allowing for real-time monitoring and continuous adjustment of risk levels as new data

becomes available. This ability to dynamically update risk stratifications is particularly beneficial in personalised healthcare management, where patient conditions and risk factors may evolve over time. Finally, the PRBMCDM algorithm improves interpretability by offering a clear, step-by-step approach to risk assessment, dynamic adaptability to population-specific data, and more comprehensive integration of risk factors. These attributes make it a superior alternative to many traditional models in terms of both flexibility and accurate classification in hypertension risk stratification.

CHAPTER FIVE

5.0 CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 Conclusion

In response to the identified gaps, the study developed the PRBMCDM, a model designed to improve upon existing hypertension risk stratification techniques. The PRBMCDM incorporates multiple criteria in its decision-making process, enhancing the model's ability to provide accurate and interpretable predictions. The model was rigorously evaluated and demonstrated superior performance, achieving an AUC of 98.7%, which is significantly higher than the models reviewed in the literature.

The development of remote hypertension monitoring and risk stratification model using (PRBMCDM) represents a significant advancement in patient care. This model integrates advanced data processing and user-friendly interfaces, enabling remote monitoring and accurate risk prediction. The comprehensive system architecture facilitates timely intervention and personalised treatment plans, setting a new standard in remote healthcare systems.

Insights from focus group discussions with experienced health professionals were crucial in identifying and operationalising key risk factors for hypertension. The collaborative effort ensured a thorough analysis, leading to a solid foundation for the hypertension risk stratification model. The focus on key risk factors such as diabetes, family history, age, smoking status, and cholesterol levels was critical in refining the model's accuracy and reliability.

A detailed analysis of hypertension risk factors in the Kogi Eastern Senatorial District of Nigeria revealed significant variations based on age, gender, location, family history, diabetes status, smoking status, cholesterol levels, and hypertension grades. These variations highlight the importance of targeted interventions, particularly for high-risk groups, and underscore the need for region-specific strategies in managing hypertension.

The feature importance analysis identified the most significant indicators of hypertension, which streamlined the model and enhanced its predictive power. The study also discussed the practical implementation of the PRBMCDM model in clinical settings. The model's design allows for seamless integration into existing healthcare systems, enabling remote monitoring of patients with hypertension. This not only facilitates early detection and intervention but also supports personalised patient care by considering multiple risk factors.

The PRBMCDM approach is designed for scalability, making it adaptable to various healthcare settings, including resource-limited environments. This research aims to advance hypertension management by developing a remote monitoring tool that integrates an interpretable and transparent risk stratification model. By enhancing accessibility to care in high-burden areas, the model empowers healthcare professionals to make informed decisions, ultimately improving patient outcomes. The successful deployment of PRBMCDM has the potential to reduce hypertension-related complications and mortality in LMICs, contributing to global efforts in combating cardiovascular diseases.

5.2 Recommendation

- i. The developed remote hypertension monitoring and risk stratification model using PRBMCDM algorithm should be incorporated into healthcare systems, particularly in low- and middle-income settings where hypertension monitoring remains a significant challenge. By leveraging the model's interpretability and adaptability, it can enhance clinical decision-making and support targeted interventions.
- ii. While the PRBMCDM model demonstrates robust performance in simulation and testing environments, it is crucial to validate its utility in real-world clinical settings. Pilot studies in hospitals or community health centres can assess its scalability, reliability, and impact on patient outcomes.
- iii. Integrating real-time data from wearable devices and IoT technologies can enhance the model's responsiveness to patient health changes.

5.3 Contributions to Knowledge

- i. A mathematical framework using the Percentile Rank-Based Multi-Criteria Decision Model (PRBMCDM) was developed.
- ii. An algorithm for PRBMCDM-based hypertension risk stratification model was developed.
- iii. A model with predictive accuracy of 98.7% compared to other existing models in the literature was developed
- iv. A model with the ability to balance predictive accuracy with clinical interpretability was developed.

5.4 Suggestions for Further Studies

Future work will focus on the following:

- i. Further validation of the model across diverse populations
- ii. Investigation of the model's applicability to other chronic diseases
- iii. Model's refinement with a view of enhancing its user-friendliness and integration into various healthcare sectors.

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APPENDICES

Appendix A: Request Letter for Ethical Clearance

Department of Computer Science,
Kogi State College of Education,
Ankpa.
15th November, 2021.

The Permanent Secretary,
Kogi State Ministry of Health,
Lokoja, Kogi State.

Dear Sir/Madam,

Request for Ethical Clearance for the Study: “Development of a Naïve Bayes Based Remote Health Monitoring model for hypertension Risk Stratification”

I am writing to formally request ethical clearance from the Kogi State Ministry of Health for my research study titled “Development of a Naïve Bayes Based Remote Health Monitoring model for hypertension Risk Stratification.” This study is part of my academic work towards the completion of my PhD at Federal University of Technology, Minna, and aims to develop an innovative system for monitoring hypertension and stratifying risk using remote technologies.

The research will involve the organisation of focus group discussion comprises of medical personels and collection of health-related data from hypertensive patients in healthcare facilities within Kogi State, and will be conducted in compliance with all relevant ethical standards for patient privacy, confidentiality, and data security. The objective is to improve hypertension management through real-time monitoring and risk stratification, particularly benefiting patients in remote and underserved areas. All necessary steps will be taken to ensure that participants’ rights and well-being are fully protected throughout the study.

Enclosed with this letter is a detailed proposal of the study, including the methodology, objectives. I kindly request that you review the provided documentation and grant ethical clearance to proceed with the study.

I would be grateful for the Ministry’s approval and any further guidance or recommendations necessary to ensure the study aligns with state and national health regulations. Please do not hesitate to contact me at 07060624365, 07018805339 or onuचेgideonatabo@gmail.com for any additional information or clarifications.

Thank you for considering this request. I look forward to your favorable response.

Yours sincerely,

Atabo Onuche Gideon

APPENDIX B: Ethical Clearance Certificate

MOH/PRS/465/V.1/015

10/2/2022

ETHICAL CLEARANCE CERTIFICATE

This is to Certify that the Methodology Adopted by

ATABO ONUCHE GIDEON

PhD/SICT/2019/9834

For the study

'Development of a naïve bayes based remote health monitoring model for hypertension risk stratification''

Will not in any way impinge on the Ethical Standard of Medical Practice in Kogi State, Nigeria.

DR. BARNABAS SEGUN ISAAC

Chairman, Health Research Ethics Committee.

APPENDIX C: REMOTE MONITORING INTERFACE

User ID:

New User? [Register Now](#)
A Doctor? [Doctor Login](#)

Patient and doctor login menu

Demographic Information Form

User ID:	<input type="text" value="333"/>
Name:	<input type="text" value="XXX"/>
Age:	<input type="text" value="46"/>
Gender:	<input type="text" value="Male"/>
Total Cholesterol (mg/dl):	<input type="text" value="102"/>
Family History of Hypertension:	<input type="text" value="No"/>
Diabetes Status:	<input type="text" value="No"/>
Smoking Status:	<input type="text" value="No"/>
Doctor:	<input type="text" value="Dr. XY"/>
Doctor Phone:	<input type="text" value="07018805339"/>
Doctor Email:	<input type="text" value="onuchegideonatabo@gmail.com"/>

Already Registered? [Login](#)

Patient Demographic and clinical information form

Doctor Registration Form

NAME:	Dr. XY
Doctor AS:	Cardiology
Doctor LN:	XXXXXXXX
Doctor Phone:	07018805339
Doctor Email:	onuchegideonatabo@gmail.com

[Submit](#)

Already Registered? [Login](#)

Doctor registration form

Age: 46 | Gender: Male | TCH: 102 | Family History: no |
Diabetes: no | Smoking: no

Systolic Blood Pressure (mmHg)

Diastolic Blood Pressure (mmHg)

[Run Simulation](#) [Reset](#) [Logout](#)

[Open Doctor Interface](#)

Interface to input systolic and diastolic blood pressure

Simulation Results

Risk Grade: Grade 3 hypertension

Damage Level: 5

Risk Level: High risk

Critical risk level! Please contact your doctor immediately.

Reset

Interface for simulation result

Dr. YYY [Logout](#) [Dashboard](#)

Patients

ZZZ

ZZZ's Medical Records

Systolic BP	Diastolic BP	Risk Grade	Damage Level	Time/Date	Doctor	Doctor's Advice
157	100	Grade 2 hypertension	4	2024-07-12 04:59:35	Not Seen	Not commented yet.
150	90	Grade 1 hypertension	3	2024-07-12 04:59:09	Not Seen	Not commented yet.
140	90	Grade 1 hypertension	3	2024-07-12 04:58:02	Not Seen	Not commented yet.
180	110	Grade 3 hypertension	5	2024-07-12 04:57:13	Not Seen	Not commented yet.
172	100	Grade 2 hypertension	4	2024-07-12 04:56:51	Not Seen	Not commented yet.
157	100	Grade 2 hypertension	4	2024-07-12 04:53:57	Not Seen	Not commented yet.

Interface for patient medical result

APPENDIX D

SOURCE CODE LISTING

```
# -*- coding: utf-8 -*-
"""
Created on Thu Jul 18 02:49:23 2024

import tkinter as tk
from tkinter import filedialog, messagebox, Toplevel, ttk
import pandas as pd
from sklearn.metrics import roc_curve, auc, confusion_matrix
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
from matplotlib.backends.backend_tkagg import FigureCanvasTkAgg
import seaborn as sns

class HealthRiskModel:
    def __init__(self):
        self.beta_1 = 0
        self.beta_2 = 0
        self.data = None

    def upload_file(self):
        file_path = filedialog.askopenfilename()
        if not file_path:
            return
        try:
            self.data = pd.read_excel(file_path)
            self.data['AGE'] = pd.to_numeric(self.data['AGE'], errors='coerce')
            self.data['SEX'] = self.data['SEX'].str.upper()
            self.data = self.data[self.data['SEX'].isin(['MALE', 'FEMALE'])]
```

```

self.data = self.data.dropna(subset=['AGE', 'SEX', 'FHH', 'DBM', 'S.S', 'TCH', 'HG',
'HRL'])
messagebox.showinfo("Info", "Dataset uploaded successfully")
except Exception as e:
    messagebox.showerror("Error", f"Failed to upload dataset: {e}")

def calculate_G(self, hypertension_grade):
    if hypertension_grade == 'Grade 1':
        return 1
    elif hypertension_grade == 'Grade 2':
        return 2
    elif hypertension_grade == 'Grade 3':
        return 3
    else:
        return 0

def calculate_A(self, age, sex):
    if (sex == 'MALE' and age >= 65) or (sex == 'FEMALE' and age >= 55):
        return 1
    else:
        return 0

def calculate_total_risk_score(self, row):
    G = self.calculate_G(row['HG'])
    A = self.calculate_A(row['AGE'], row['SEX'])
    FHH = 1 if row['FHH'] == 'YES' else 0
    D = 1 if row['DBM'] == 'YES' else 0
    S = 1 if row['S.S'] == 'Smoker' else 0
    C = 1 if row['TCH'] == '200 or above' else 0

    alpha = G + FHH + D + S + C + A
    return alpha

```

```

def determine_risk_level(self, alpha):
    if alpha <= self.beta_1:
        return 'Low Risk'
    elif self.beta_1 < alpha <= self.beta_2:
        return 'Medium Risk'
    else:
        return 'High Risk'

def train_and_evaluate_model(self):
    self.data['Total Risk Score'] = self.data.apply(self.calculate_total_risk_score, axis=1)
    self.data['Risk Level Numeric'] = self.data['HRL'].map({'Low Risk': 1, 'Medium Risk': 2,
'High Risk': 3})

    skf = StratifiedKFold(n_splits=5)
    self.fold_metrics = []
    all_y_true = []
    all_y_pred = []

    for train_index, test_index in skf.split(self.data, self.data['Risk Level Numeric']):
        train_data = self.data.iloc[train_index]
        test_data = self.data.iloc[test_index]

        self.beta_1 = train_data['Total Risk Score'].quantile(0.33)
        self.beta_2 = train_data['Total Risk Score'].quantile(0.67)

        test_data['Calculated Risk Level'] = test_data['Total Risk
Score'].apply(self.determine_risk_level)
        test_data['Calculated Numeric'] = test_data['Calculated Risk Level'].map({'Low Risk':
1, 'Medium Risk': 2, 'High Risk': 3})

        y_true = test_data['Risk Level Numeric']
        y_pred = test_data['Calculated Numeric']

```

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        all_y_true.extend(y_true)
        all_y_pred.extend(y_pred)
class GUI:
    def __init__(self, root, model):
        self.root = root
        self.model = model
        self.init_ui()

    def init_ui(self):
        self.root.title("Health Risk Prediction System")
        self.root.geometry("900x700")

        self.upload_button = tk.Button(self.root, text="Upload Dataset",
command=self.model.upload_file)
        self.upload_button.pack()

        self.train_button = tk.Button(self.root, text="Train Model", command=self.train_model)
        self.train_button.pack()

        self.roc_button = tk.Button(self.root, text="Show ROC Curve",
command=self.show_roc_curve)
        self.roc_button.pack()

        self.cm_button = tk.Button(self.root, text="Show Confusion Matrix",
command=self.show_confusion_matrix)
        self.cm_button.pack()

        self.freq_button = tk.Button(self.root, text="Show Frequency Table",
command=self.show_frequency_table)
        self.freq_button.pack()

        self.dataset_button = tk.Button(self.root, text="Show Uploaded Dataset",
command=self.show_uploaded_dataset)

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self.dataset_button.pack()

self.form_frame = tk.Frame(self.root)
self.form_frame.pack(pady=10)

tk.Label(self.form_frame, text="Age").grid(row=0, column=0, padx=10, pady=5)
self.age_entry = tk.Entry(self.form_frame)
self.age_entry.grid(row=0, column=1, padx=10, pady=5)

self.sex_var = tk.StringVar(value="MALE")
tk.Label(self.form_frame, text="Sex").grid(row=0, column=2, padx=10, pady=5)
tk.Radiobutton(self.form_frame, text="Male", variable=self.sex_var,
value="MALE").grid(row=0, column=3, padx=10, pady=5)
tk.Radiobutton(self.form_frame, text="Female", variable=self.sex_var,
value="FEMALE").grid(row=0, column=4, padx=10, pady=5)

self.fhh_var = tk.StringVar(value="NO")
tk.Label(self.form_frame, text="Family Health History").grid(row=1, column=0,
padx=10, pady=5)
tk.Radiobutton(self.form_frame, text="Yes", variable=self.fhh_var,
value="YES").grid(row=1, column=1, padx=10, pady=5)
tk.Radiobutton(self.form_frame, text="No", variable=self.fhh_var,
value="NO").grid(row=1, column=2, padx=10, pady=5)

self.dbm_var = tk.StringVar(value="NO")
tk.Label(self.form_frame, text="Diabetes Mellitus").grid(row=1, column=3, padx=10,
pady=5)
tk.Radiobutton(self.form_frame, text="Yes", variable=self.dbm_var,
value="YES").grid(row=1, column=4, padx=10, pady=5)
tk.Radiobutton(self.form_frame, text="No", variable=self.dbm_var,
value="NO").grid(row=1, column=5, padx=10, pady=5)

self.ss_var = tk.StringVar(value="Non-Smoker")

```

```

tk.Label(self.form_frame, text="Smoking Status").grid(row=2, column=0, padx=10,
pady=5)
tk.Radiobutton(self.form_frame, text="Smoker", variable=self.ss_var,
value="Smoker").grid(row=2, column=1, padx=10, pady=5)
tk.Radiobutton(self.form_frame, text="Non-Smoker", variable=self.ss_var, value="Non-
Smoker").grid(row=2, column=2, padx=10, pady=5)

self.tch_var = tk.StringVar(value="Below 200")
tk.Label(self.form_frame, text="Total Cholesterol").grid(row=2, column=3, padx=10,
pady=5)
tk.Radiobutton(self.form_frame, text="200 or above", variable=self.tch_var, value="200
or above").grid(row=2, column=4, padx=10, pady=5)
tk.Radiobutton(self.form_frame, text="Below 200", variable=self.tch_var, value="Below
200").grid(row=2, column=5, padx=10, pady=5)

self.hg_var = tk.StringVar(value="None")
tk.Label(self.form_frame, text="Hypertension Grade").grid(row=3, column=0, padx=10,
pady=5)
tk.Radiobutton(self.form_frame, text="Grade 1", variable=self.hg_var, value="Grade
1").grid(row=3, column=1, padx=10, pady=5)
tk.Radiobutton(self.form_frame, text="Grade 2", variable=self.hg_var, value="Grade
2").grid(row=3, column=2, padx=10, pady=5)
tk.Radiobutton(self.form_frame, text="Grade 3", variable=self.hg_var, value="Grade
3").grid(row=3, column=3, padx=10, pady=5)
tk.Radiobutton(self.form_frame, text="None", variable=self.hg_var,
value="None").grid(row=3, column=4, padx=10, pady=5)

self.predict_button = tk.Button(self.root, text="Predict Risk",
command=self.predict_risk)
self.predict_button.pack(pady=10)

self.result_label = tk.Label(self.root, text="Predicted Risk Level: ")
self.result_label.pack()

```

```

def train_model(self):
    beta_1, beta_2 = self.model.train_model()
    self.display_thresholds(beta_1, beta_2)
    messagebox.showinfo("Info", "Model trained successfully")

def display_thresholds(self, beta_1, beta_2):
    threshold_label = tk.Label(self.root, text=f"Thresholds:  $\beta_1$ ={beta_1:.2f},
 $\beta_2$ ={beta_2:.2f}")
    threshold_label.place(x=700, y=10)

def show_roc_curve(self):
    new_window = Toplevel(self.root)
    new_window.title("ROC Curve")
    new_window.geometry("800x600")

    y_true = self.model.data['HRL'].apply(lambda x: 1 if x == 'High Risk' else 0)
    y_scores = self.model.data['Total Risk Score']
    if y_true.sum() == 0:
        messagebox.showinfo("Info", "No positive samples in y_true, ROC curve cannot be
plotted.")
        return

    fpr, tpr, _ = roc_curve(y_true, y_scores)
    roc_auc = auc(fpr, tpr)

    fig, ax = plt.subplots()
    ax.plot(fpr, tpr, color='darkorange', lw=2, label=f'ROC curve (area = {roc_auc:.2f})')
    ax.plot([0, 1], [0, 1], color='navy', lw=2, linestyle='--')
    ax.set_xlim([0.0, 1.0])
    ax.set_ylim([0.0, 1.05])
    ax.set_xlabel('False Positive Rate')
    ax.set_ylabel('True Positive Rate')

```

```

ax.set_title('Receiver Operating Characteristic')
ax.legend(loc="lower right")

canvas = FigureCanvasTkAgg(fig, master=new_window)
canvas.draw()
canvas.get_tk_widget().pack()

def show_confusion_matrix(self):
    new_window = Toplevel(self.root)
    new_window.title("Confusion Matrix")
    new_window.geometry("800x600")

    true_labels = self.model.data['HRL']
    predicted_labels = self.model.data['Calculated Risk Level']

    cm = confusion_matrix(true_labels, predicted_labels, labels=['Low Risk', 'Medium
Risk', 'High Risk'])
    fig, ax = plt.subplots()
    sns.heatmap(cm, annot=True, fmt="d", cmap="Blues", xticklabels=['Low Risk',
'Medium Risk', 'High Risk'], yticklabels=['Low Risk', 'Medium Risk', 'High Risk'])
    ax.set_xlabel('Predicted')
    ax.set_ylabel('True')
    ax.set_title('Confusion Matrix')

    canvas = FigureCanvasTkAgg(fig, master=new_window)
    canvas.draw()
    canvas.get_tk_widget().pack()

def show_frequency_table(self):
    new_window = Toplevel(self.root)
    new_window.title("Frequency Table")
    new_window.geometry("400x300")

```

```

freq_table = self.model.data['HRL'].value_counts().reset_index()
freq_table.columns = ['Risk Level', 'Frequency']

tree = ttk.Treeview(new_window)
tree.pack(expand=True, fill=tk.BOTH)

tree["columns"] = list(freq_table.columns)
tree["show"] = "headings"

for col in freq_table.columns:
    tree.heading(col, text=col)
    tree.column(col, width=100)

for index, row in freq_table.iterrows():
    tree.insert("", "end", values=list(row))

def show_uploaded_dataset(self):
    new_window = Toplevel(self.root)
    new_window.title("Uploaded Dataset")
    new_window.geometry("800x600")

    tree = ttk.Treeview(new_window)
    tree.pack(expand=True, fill=tk.BOTH)

    tree["columns"] = list(self.model.data.columns)
    tree["show"] = "headings"

    for col in self.model.data.columns:
        tree.heading(col, text=col)
        tree.column(col, width=100)

    for index, row in self.model.data.iterrows():
        tree.insert("", "end", values=list(row))

```

```

def predict_risk(self):
    try:
        age = int(self.age_entry.get())
        sex = self.sex_var.get()
        fhh = self.fhh_var.get()
        dbm = self.dbm_var.get()
        ss = self.ss_var.get()
        tch = self.tch_var.get()
        hg = self.hg_var.get()

        patient_data = {'AGE': age, 'SEX': sex, 'FHH': fhh, 'DBM': dbm, 'S.S': ss, 'TCH': tch,
'HG': hg}
        alpha = self.model.calculate_total_risk_score(patient_data)
        risk_level = self.model.determine_risk_level(alpha)

        self.result_label.config(text=f"Predicted Risk Level: {risk_level}")
    except ValueError as e:
        messagebox.showerror("Error", f"Invalid input: {e}")

if __name__ == "__main__":
    root = tk.Tk()
    model = HealthRiskModel()
    app = GUI(root, model)
    root.mainloop()

import pandas as pd
from sklearn.model_selection import train_test_split
from sklearn.naive_bayes import GaussianNB
from sklearn.metrics import accuracy_score

# S = pd.read_csv('hypertension_data.csv')

```

```

}

# Convert categorical variables to numeric
df = pd.DataFrame(data)
df['Gender'] = df['Gender'].map({'M': 0, 'F': 1})
df['OCCP'] = df['OCCP'].astype('category').cat.codes
df['LOC'] = df['LOC'].astype('category').cat.codes

# Split data into features and target variable
X = df.drop('Hypertension', axis=1)
y = df['Hypertension']

# Fit the baseline model with all features
model = GaussianNB()
model.fit(X_train, y_train)
baseline_accuracy = accuracy_score(y_test, model.predict(X_test))

# Calculate feature importance by dropping each feature
feature_importances = {}
for feature in X.columns:
    # Drop the feature from the dataset
    X_train_reduced = X_train.drop(columns=[feature])
    X_test_reduced = X_test.drop(columns=[feature])

    # Fit the model without the feature
    model.fit(X_train_reduced, y_train)
    reduced_accuracy = accuracy_score(y_test, model.predict(X_test_reduced))

    # Calculate the importance score
    importance_score = baseline_accuracy - reduced_accuracy
    feature_importances[feature] = importance_score

```

```
# Sort feature importances in descending order
sorted_features = sorted(feature_importances.items(), key=lambda x: x[1], reverse=True)

# Display the results in a table
importance_df = pd.DataFrame(sorted_features, columns=['Feature', 'Importance Score'])
importance_df['Baseline Accuracy'] = baseline_accuracy
importance_df['Reduced Accuracy'] = importance_df['Baseline Accuracy'] -
importance_df['Importance Score']

# Print the importance table
print(importance_df)
```